

Derivation notes for

The generation of 150 km echoes through nonlinear wave mode coupling

William J. Longley

Center for Solar-Terrestrial Research, New Jersey Institute of Technology, Newark, NJ, USA

1 Introduction

2 In this text, the results from the manuscript are derived step by step. Due to the
3 length of this, equations are not numbered explicitly. Those equations that are found in
4 the main text will be numbered the same as the main text in order to provide cross-
5 reference. Additionally, most of the text in Section 2 is repeated here to keep the long
6 derivation consistent with the outlined derivation in the main text.

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32 1. Fourier-Laplace Transforming the Boltzmann Equation

33 Goal: To determine how the high frequency Langmuir or Upper-Hybrid mode can
 34 enhance the low frequency ion-acoustic mode (Note: Langmuir and Upper-Hybrid are
 35 sometimes used interchangeably. In such a context, the Langmuir mode is the
 36 unmagnetized limit of the Upper-Hybrid mode). The Upper-Hybrid mode/plasma line is
 37 observed to be enhanced by photoelectrons, and we want to know how/if the ion line
 38 power is also enhanced.

39 The starting point for this derivation is the Boltzmann equation:

$$40 \frac{\partial F_s[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla_x F_s[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{E}[t, \vec{x}] + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \cdot \nabla_v F_s[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] = S[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] \quad (1)$$

41 This equation is derived in *Nicholson* (1983) and written in the same form as *Froula et al.*
 42 *al.* (2011). The left-hand side is the total time derivative of the distribution F_s of species
 43 s . The right-hand side represents discontinuities in the total time derivative as collisions,
 44 with the collision operator S to be specified later. The convention used in this paper for
 45 distribution functions is that

$$46 F_s(\vec{v}) = n_s f_s(\vec{v})$$

47 where the normalizations are

$$48 \int d\vec{v}^3 F_s(\vec{v}) = n_s$$

$$49 \int d\vec{v}^3 f_s(\vec{v}) = 1$$

50 which defines the density n_s .

51 The process of linearization is to assume each variable quantity can be
 52 decomposed into a 0th order term, and a small 1st order perturbation:

$$53 F_s = F_{0s} + F_{1s}, \quad (2)$$

$$54 \vec{E} = \vec{E}_0 + \vec{E}_1, \quad (3)$$

$$55 \vec{B} = \vec{B}_0 + \vec{B}_1. \quad (4)$$

56 We assume electrostatic waves ($B_1 = 0$), and that no 0th order electric field is present
 57 ($E_0 = 0$). Putting the perturbation scheme (Eq 2-4) into the Boltzmann equation yields

$$58 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (F_{0s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] + F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]) + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla_x (F_{0s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] + F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]) \\ 59 + \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{E}_1[t, \vec{x}] + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}_0) \cdot \nabla_v (F_{0s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] + F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]) = S[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]. \quad (5)$$

60 All the 0th order terms can be collected together:

$$\begin{aligned}
62 \quad & \left\{ \frac{\partial F_{0s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla_x F_{0s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}_0) \cdot \nabla_v F_{0s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] \right\} \\
63 \quad & + \left\{ \frac{\partial F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla_x F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[t, \vec{x}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{0s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] \right. \\
64 \quad & \left. + \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}_0) \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] \right\} + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[t, \vec{x}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] = S[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]. \\
65 \quad & \tag{6}
\end{aligned}$$

66 The zeroth order terms are simple and setting f_{0s} to an unchanging Maxwellian
67 leads to the first set of brackets evaluating to 0. This leaves

$$\begin{aligned}
68 \quad & \left\{ \frac{\partial F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla_x F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[t, \vec{x}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{0s}[\vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}_0) \right. \\
69 \quad & \left. \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] \right\} + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[t, \vec{x}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] = S[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]. \\
70 \quad & \tag{7}
\end{aligned}$$

71 Typically, the next step is to linearize equation 7 by keeping only the first order terms
72 (the bracketed terms). The argument is that the zeroth order distribution is chosen such
73 that the first order distribution is a small perturbation, and since $E_1 \propto f_{1s}$ from Gauss'
74 law, the term $\vec{E}_1 \cdot \nabla_v f_{1s}$ is the product of two small quantities, and therefore is an even
75 smaller quantity. Thus, only the terms in the brackets are retained, and the resulting
76 equation is linear as it only contains single factors of f_{1s} or E_1 .

77 The basis of the mode coupling developed here is to retain the nonlinear term $\vec{E}_1 \cdot$
78 $\nabla_v f_{1s}$ in equation (7). In the case of instability, the perturbed electric field can have
79 significant amplitude and therefore the nonlinear term is no longer a small quantity.

80 The next step in a typical linear solution is to Fourier-Laplace transform the
81 linearized version of equation 7. We will therefore do the same Fourier-Laplace
82 transform of equation 7, including the nonlinear term. In this paper we use the non-
83 unitary convention for the Fourier transform, defined as

$$84 \quad \hat{f}(k) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) e^{-ikx} dx. \tag{8}$$

85 As discussed in texts such as *Nicholson* (1983), the time variable must be Laplace
86 transformed instead of Fourier transformed in order to accommodate Landau damping.
87 The convention we use for the Laplace transform is

$$88 \quad \hat{f}(\omega) = \int_0^{\infty} f(t) e^{i(\omega - i\gamma)t} dt. \tag{9}$$

89 In applying the Fourier-Laplace transform to equation 7, the linear terms are
90 straightforward and transform as

$$91 \quad \frac{\partial F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]}{\partial t} \Rightarrow -i(\omega - i\gamma)F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}], \tag{10}$$

92
$$\vec{v} \cdot \nabla_x F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] \Rightarrow i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{v})F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}], \quad (11)$$

93
$$\frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[t, \vec{x}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \rightarrow \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{0s}[\vec{v}], \quad (12)$$

94
$$\frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] \Rightarrow \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]. \quad (13)$$

95 In equation 10 an initial value term results from the Laplace transform, as an integration
96 by parts is used to evaluate the time derivative.

97 The Fourier-Laplace transforms in equations 10 – 13 are straightforward because
98 each term is linear, and therefore only one function of t or x is present. However, the
99 nonlinear term in equation 7 is a product of two functions that depend on both space and
100 time. The Fourier transform of a product of functions is a convolution:

101
$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)g(x) e^{-ikx} dx = \frac{1}{2\pi} (\hat{f} \star \hat{g})(k), \quad (14)$$

102 where $\star$ is the convolution operator. The convolution can be worked out to the single
103 integral

104
$$(\hat{f} \star \hat{g})(k) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(k - \kappa)g(\kappa) d\kappa. \quad (15)$$

105 By symmetry of the product, this is equivalent to

106
$$(\hat{f} \star \hat{g})(k) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\kappa)g(k - \kappa) d\kappa$$

107 Notice that the Fourier transform of the product results in an integration over a
108 dummy wavenumber κ , where one function is evaluated at κ and the other is evaluated at
109 $k - \kappa$. This integration over all wavenumbers (and later frequencies) is how the nonlinear
110 term allows different wave modes to interact.

111 Making the obvious substitution of $f \rightarrow \vec{E}_1$ and $g \rightarrow \nabla_v f_{1s}$, we find the Fourier
112 transform of the electric field term is

113
$$\mathcal{F}_k \left\{ \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1 \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s} \right\} = \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \vec{E}_1(t, \vec{k} - \vec{\kappa}) \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(t, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v}) d\vec{\kappa} \quad (13)$$

114 Note that the 2π factor is cubed since the Fourier transform is over the $d\vec{k}$ space in $\mathbb{R}^3$,
115 so the Fourier transform is applied 3 times.

116 We still need to Laplace transform the $E_1 f_1$ term in time. The convolution integral
117 for the Laplace transform $\mathcal{L}$ is

118
$$\mathcal{L}\{f(t)g(t)\} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{f}(-iv)\hat{g}(-i(\omega - v) - \gamma) dv$$

119 And again by symmetry of the product the following is equivalent:

120
$$\mathcal{L}\{f(t)g(t)\} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{f}(-i(\omega - v) - \gamma)\hat{g}(-iv) dv$$

121 Then the Laplace transform of the nonlinear term is

$$122 \quad \mathcal{L}_\omega \left\{ \mathcal{F}_k \left\{ \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1 \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s} \right\} \right\} = \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \mathcal{L}_\omega \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \vec{E}_1(t, \vec{k} - \vec{\kappa}) \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(t, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v}) d\vec{\kappa} \right\}$$

123 We assume the functions for the electric field and distribution are continuous, so we can
124 move the Laplace transform integral inside the Fourier transform integrals

$$125 \quad \mathcal{L}_\omega \left\{ \mathcal{F}_k \left\{ \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1 \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s} \right\} \right\} = \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathcal{L} \{ \vec{E}_1(t, \vec{k} - \vec{\kappa}) \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(t, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v}) \} d\vec{\kappa}$$

126 Identifying the variables in the convolution integral as $\hat{f} \rightarrow \nabla_v F_{1s}$, and $\hat{g} \rightarrow E_1$, we get

$$127 \quad \mathcal{L}_\omega \left\{ \mathcal{F}_k \left\{ \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1 \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s} \right\} \right\}$$

$$128 \quad = \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv \vec{E}_1(-i(\omega - \nu) - \gamma, \vec{k} - \vec{\kappa})$$

$$129 \quad \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(-i\nu, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v})$$

130 It may also be convenient to use the equivalent form of

$$131 \quad \mathcal{L}_\omega \left\{ \mathcal{F}_k \left\{ \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1 \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s} \right\} \right\}$$

$$132 \quad = \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv \vec{E}_1(-i\nu, \vec{\kappa})$$

$$133 \quad \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(-i(\omega - \nu) - \gamma, \vec{k} - \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v})$$

134 The full 1st/2nd order Laplace-Fourier transformed Boltzmann equation is

$$135 \quad -i(\omega - i\gamma)F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{v})F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[\omega, \vec{k}]$$

$$136 \quad \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]$$

$$137 \quad + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv \vec{E}_1(-i\nu, \vec{\kappa})$$

$$138 \quad \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(-i(\omega - \nu) - \gamma, \vec{k} - \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v}) = \mathcal{F}_{\omega k} \{ S[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] \}$$

139 We can resolve a notational issue with the Laplace transform of the second order term.

140 Since the first term shows the Laplace transform of F_{1s} is $F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]$, we can
141 effectively factor out the $-i$ in the argument and stay consistent in the meaning of the
142 Laplace transformed functions. Then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
143 \quad & -i(\omega - i\gamma)F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{v})F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \\
144 \quad & \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \\
145 \quad & + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv \vec{E}_1[v, \vec{k}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[(\omega - v), \vec{k} - \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \\
146 \quad & = \mathcal{F}_{\omega k} \{S[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]\}
\end{aligned}$$

147 In hindsight, the alternative form of the Fourier and Laplace transforms
148 (switching the order of the product $E_1 \nabla_v F_1$) proves more useful:

$$\begin{aligned}
149 \quad & -i(\omega - i\gamma)F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{v})F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \\
150 \quad & \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[\omega - i\gamma, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \\
151 \quad & + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv \vec{E}_1[\omega - v, \vec{k} - \vec{k}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
152 \quad & = \mathcal{F}_{\omega k} \{S[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}]\}
\end{aligned}$$

153 At this time, we must now specify the collision operator. Physically, Coulomb
154 collisions are an important process, however an analytic solution for the Fokker-Planck
155 collision operator is not supported in this framework (see *Kudeki and Milla, 2011; Milla*
156 *and Kudeki, 2011; and Longley et al., 2019*). Instead, we use the BGK operator as it has
157 the advantage of being linear, and it adequately describes electron-neutral collisions:

$$158 \quad S[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] = -\nu_s \left(F_{1s}[t, \vec{x}, \vec{v}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t, \vec{x}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right), \quad (16)$$

159 where ν_{cs} is the collision rate, and the zeroth and first order densities relate to the
160 distribution functions as $n_{0s} = \int d\vec{v}^3 F_{0s}[\vec{v}]$ and $n_{1s} = \int d\vec{v}^3 F_{1s}[\vec{v}]$.

161 The full Fourier-Laplace transform of equation 7 is then

$$\begin{aligned}
162 \quad & \{-i\omega - \nu_s + i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{v})\} F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \\
163 \quad & \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \\
164 \quad & = -\frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv \vec{E}_1[\omega - v, \vec{k} - \vec{k}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
165 \quad & + \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}]. \\
166 \quad & \hspace{20em} (17)
\end{aligned}$$

167
168
169
170

171 **2. Solving for Density Perturbations**

172 *Froula et al.* (2011) derives the scattering power of a collisional plasma as

173
$$S(\omega, \vec{k}) = 2\nu_q \left\langle |n_{1e}(\omega, \vec{k})|^2 \right\rangle \quad (18)$$

174 where ν_q is the collision frequency for electrons or ions, determined by the distribution
 175 being ensemble averaged. The quantity $S(\omega, \vec{k})$ is analogous to a scattering cross section
 176 in the radar equation:

177
$$P_{rec} = P_{tr} \frac{r_0^2}{2\pi A} S(\omega, \vec{k}). \quad (19)$$

178 This means to determine the scattering spectra of 150-km echoes, we need to
 179 solve the Fourier-Laplace transformed Boltzmann equation (Eq. 17) for the electron
 180 density perturbations n_{1e} .

181 The main text thoroughly discusses Equations (20) – (27) and the need for
 182 separating the nonlinear terms at ω^{hf} and $\omega - \omega^{hf}$ from the linear terms.

183 The nonlinear Fourier-Laplace transform in equation (17) is solved for the
 184 perturbed distribution term. First, the $v \times B$ term can be simplified as (see *Froula et al.*,
 185 2011):

186
$$\vec{v} \times \vec{B} \cdot \nabla_v f_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] = -B \frac{\partial f_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]}{\partial \phi}$$

187 So the Boltzmann equation becomes

188
$$\{-i\omega - \nu_s + i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{v})\} F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \frac{q_s}{m_s} \vec{E}_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}] - \frac{q_s B}{m_s}$$

189
$$\cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} f_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]$$

190
$$= -\frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv \vec{E}_1[\omega - \nu, \vec{k} - \vec{k}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(\nu, \vec{k}, \vec{v})$$

191
$$+ \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}].$$

192

193 Gauss' law is

194
$$\nabla \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0}$$

195 So Fourier-Laplace transforming this, our convention takes $\nabla \rightarrow i\vec{k}$, so we have

196
$$i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{E}[\omega, \vec{k}] = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \rho[\omega, \vec{k}]$$

197 Solving for E , where we move to perturbed quantities,

198
$$\vec{E}_1[\omega, \vec{k}] = -\frac{i}{\epsilon_0} \frac{\vec{k}}{k^2} \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}]$$

199 Putting this into the linear terms in the Boltzmann equation

200
$$\{-i\omega - \nu_s + i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{v})\} F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - i \frac{q_s}{\epsilon_0 m_s} \frac{\vec{k}}{k^2} \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}] - \frac{q_s B}{m_s}$$

201
$$\cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} f_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]$$

202
$$= -\frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\nu \vec{E}_1[\omega - \nu, \vec{k} - \vec{\kappa}] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(\nu, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v})$$

203
$$+ \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}].$$

204 Defining the difference in wavenumbers and frequencies, substituting the plasma
205 frequency $\omega_{ps}^2 = q_s^2 n_0 / \epsilon_0 m_s$, then simplifying,

206
$$\omega^* = \omega - \nu$$

207
$$k^* = k - \kappa$$

208
$$\{-i\omega - \nu_s + i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{v})\} F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{q_s n_0} \frac{\vec{k}}{k^2} \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}] - \frac{q_s B}{m_s}$$

209
$$\cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} f_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]$$

210
$$= -\frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\nu \vec{E}_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(\nu, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v})$$

211
$$+ \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}]$$

212 We will take the nonlinear equation and put it in the form the form $a \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} F_{1s} + p(\phi) F_{1s} =$
213 $q(\phi)$, using $\vec{k} \cdot \vec{v} = k_{\perp} v_{\perp} \cos(\phi - \delta) + k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel}$, and defining $\omega_{cs} = q_s B / m_s$, which carries
214 the sign of q_s (Ω_{cs} will be the positive-definite quantity):

215
$$-\omega_{cs} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \{-i\omega - \gamma + ik_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} + ik_{\perp} v_{\perp} \cos(\phi - \delta)\} F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]$$

216
$$= i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}]$$

217
$$- \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\nu \vec{E}_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(\nu, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v}) + F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]$$

218
$$+ \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}]$$

219 Note this is already assuming $\rho_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]$ and $F_{1s}[\nu, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v}]$ are not related to $F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]$,
220 since we will be taking $\nu \approx \omega^{hf}$ later on (and therefore $\omega^* \approx -\omega^{hf}$). Then

$$\begin{aligned}
221 \quad & -\omega_{cs} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \{-i\omega - \gamma + ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} + ik_{\perp}v_{\perp} \cos(\phi - \delta)\} F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \\
222 \quad & = i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}] \\
223 \quad & - \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv \vec{E}_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) + F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \\
224 \quad & + v_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}]
\end{aligned}$$

225 This is now in the form $a \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} F_{1s} + p(\phi) F_{1s} = q(\phi)$, which we can recast as
226 $\frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} F_{1s} + P(\phi) F_{1s} = Q(\phi)$ where $P(\phi) = p(\phi)/a$ and $Q(\phi) = q(\phi)/a$:

$$\begin{aligned}
227 \quad & \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - \frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \{-i\omega - \gamma + ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} + ik_{\perp}v_{\perp} \cos(\phi - \delta)\} F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \\
228 \quad & = -i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{\omega_{cs} k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}] \\
229 \quad & + \frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv \vec{E}_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
230 \quad & - \frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \left\{ F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + v_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

231 The solution for this is

$$232 \quad F_{1s} = e^{-\int P(\phi) d\phi} \int Q(\phi) e^{\int P(\phi') d\phi'} d\phi + C e^{-\int P(\phi) d\phi}$$

233 Which defines the integrating factor as

$$234 \quad IF = e^{\int P(\phi) d\phi}$$

235 Solving the integral,

$$\begin{aligned}
236 \quad & \int P(\phi) d\phi = \int \frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \{i\omega + \gamma - ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - ik_{\perp}v_{\perp} \cos(\phi - \delta)\} d\phi \\
237 \quad & \int P(\phi) d\phi = \frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \{i\omega + v_s - ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\} \phi - i \frac{k_{\perp}v_{\perp}}{\omega_{cs}} \sin(\phi - \delta)
\end{aligned}$$

238 The constant C is related to the initial condition $\phi = 0$, and therefore we can make the
239 choice of $C = 0$ which sets the base phase δ . The integrating factor is then

$$240 \quad IF = e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \{i\omega + v_s - ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\} \phi} e^{-ik_{\perp} \rho_s \sin(\phi)}$$

241 Where $\rho_s = v_{\perp}/\omega_{cs}$ and we need to pay attention to the sign of the charge. Then we
242 obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
243 \quad F_{1s} &= e^{\frac{-1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\psi} e^{ik_{\perp}\rho_s \sin(\psi)} \int \left[-i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{\omega_{cs}k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \nabla_v F_0[\vec{v}] \right. \\
244 \quad &+ \frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
245 \quad &- \frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \left\{ F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] \right. \\
246 \quad &\left. - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\} \left. \right] \left\{ e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\phi} e^{-ik_{\perp}\rho_s \sin(\phi)} \right\} d\phi
\end{aligned}$$

247 Note that this also substituted $\vec{E}_1 = E_1 \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*}$, meaning $\vec{E}_1$ is along the direction of $\vec{k}^*$.

248 In the integrand, the only terms with a ϕ dependence are the Landau damping
249 term: $\vec{k} \cdot \nabla_v F_0 = k_{\parallel} \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + k_{\perp} \cos \phi \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial v_{\perp}}$ and the nonlinear term: $\vec{k}^* \cdot \nabla_v F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) =$
250 $k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial f_{1s}}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + k_{\perp}^* \cos \phi \frac{\partial f_{1s}}{\partial v_{\perp}}$. We put these ϕ dependencies in, and simplify the integrating
251 factor using the identity

$$252 \quad e^{iz \sin \phi} = \sum_l J_l(z) e^{il\phi}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
253 \quad F_{1s} &= e^{\frac{-1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\psi} \sum_m J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{im\psi} \\
254 \quad &\cdot \int \left[-i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{\omega_{cs}k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \left(k_{\parallel} \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + k_{\perp} \cos \phi \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \right. \\
255 \quad &+ \frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{1}{k^*} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right. \\
256 \quad &\left. \left. + k_{\perp}^* \cos \phi \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \right. \\
257 \quad &- \frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \left\{ F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] \right. \\
258 \quad &\left. - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\} \left. \right] \left\{ e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\phi} \sum_l J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{-il\phi} \right\} d\phi
\end{aligned}$$

259 By linearity with integration/summation, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
260 \quad F_{1s} &= -\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \sum_{l,m} J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{im\psi} e^{\frac{-1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\psi} \\
261 \quad &\cdot \int \left[i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \left(k_{\parallel} \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + k_{\perp} \cos \phi \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \right. \\
262 \quad &- \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{1}{k^*} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right. \\
263 \quad &\left. \left. + k_{\perp}^* \cos \phi \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \right. \\
264 \quad &\left. + \left\{ F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] \right. \right. \\
265 \quad &\left. \left. - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\} \left\{ e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}-il\omega_{cs}\}\phi} \right\} d\phi
\end{aligned}$$

266 Looking at the integral, in the [] brackets, the only terms depending on ϕ are the Landau
267 damping and nonlinear terms (The distributions F_0 and F_1 are taken to be axisymmetric
268 and therefore have no ϕ dependence). A Bessel function identity is

$$269 \quad \sum_l J_l(z) e^{il\phi} \cos \phi = \sum_l \frac{l}{z} J_l(z) e^{il\phi}$$

270 This allows us to simplify the Landau damping term, effectively substituting $\cos \phi \rightarrow \frac{l}{z}$
271 (the l index is used since the factor $e^{-il\phi}$ is still in the integrand):

$$\begin{aligned}
272 \quad F_{1s} &= -\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \sum_{l,m} J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{im\psi} e^{\frac{-1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\psi} \\
273 \quad &\cdot \int \left[i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \left(k_{\parallel} \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + k_{\perp} \frac{l}{k_{\perp}\rho_s} \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \right. \\
274 \quad &- \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{1}{k^*} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right. \\
275 \quad &\left. \left. + k_{\perp}^* \cos \phi \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \right. \\
276 \quad &\left. + \left\{ F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] \right. \right. \\
277 \quad &\left. \left. - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\} \left\{ e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}-il\omega_{cs}\}\phi} \right\} d\phi
\end{aligned}$$

278 We then define the derivative using the notation in *Froula et al. (2011)*

$$279 \quad \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} = k_{\parallel} \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{l}{\rho_s} \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v_{\perp}}$$

280 Where the $\vec{v}^*$ is used to distinguish this from the normal velocity gradient (i.e., unrelated
281 to the ω^* and k^* variables). Then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
282 \quad F_{1s} = & -\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \sum_{l,m} J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{im\psi} e^{\frac{-1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+v_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\psi} \\
283 \quad & \cdot \int \left[i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} \right. \\
284 \quad & - \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{1}{k^*} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right. \\
285 \quad & \left. \left. + k_{\perp}^* \cos \phi \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \right. \\
286 \quad & \left. + \left\{ F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + v_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] \right. \right. \\
287 \quad & \left. \left. - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\} \right] \left\{ e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+v_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}-il\omega_{cs}\}\phi} \right\} d\phi
\end{aligned}$$

288 We can make the same substitution for the nonlinear term, noting the argument of the
289 Bessel function is what matters:

$$\begin{aligned}
290 \quad F_{1s} = & -\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \sum_{l,m} J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{im\psi} e^{\frac{-1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+v_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\psi} \\
291 \quad & \cdot \int \left[i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} \right. \\
292 \quad & - \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{1}{k^*} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right. \\
293 \quad & \left. \left. + k_{\perp}^* \frac{l}{k_{\perp}\rho_s} \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \right. \\
294 \quad & \left. + \left\{ F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + v_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] \right. \right. \\
295 \quad & \left. \left. - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\} \right] \left\{ e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+v_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}-il\omega_{cs}\}\phi} \right\} d\phi
\end{aligned}$$

296 We then define a similar modified velocity gradient as

$$297 \quad \vec{k}^* \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) = k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* l}{k_{\perp} \rho_s} \frac{\partial F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{\partial v_{\perp}}$$

298 Where we have to do some poor notation with $\vec{v}^{**}$ to denote it is the modified gradient
299 and uses the k^* wavenumber. This will be hard to keep straight, so we also rely on the
300 leading $\vec{k}^*$ factor to inform us on the wavenumber used in the gradient. We then have

$$\begin{aligned}
301 \quad F_{1s} &= -\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \sum_{l,m} J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{im\psi} e^{\frac{-1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\psi} \\
302 \quad &\cdot \int \left[i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} \right. \\
303 \quad &- \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
304 \quad &+ \left\{ F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] \right. \\
305 \quad &\left. \left. - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\} \right] \left\{ e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}-il\omega_{cs}\}\phi} \right\} d\phi
\end{aligned}$$

306 The only remaining ϕ dependence in the integral is the exponential, so we then have

$$\begin{aligned}
307 \quad F_{1s} &= -\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \sum_{l,m} J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{im\psi} e^{\frac{-1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\psi} \\
308 \quad &\cdot \left[i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} \right. \\
309 \quad &- \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
310 \quad &+ \left\{ f_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\} \\
311 \quad &\cdot \int \left\{ e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}-il\omega_{cs}\}\phi} \right\} d\phi
\end{aligned}$$

312 The integral is then trivial,

$$313 \quad \int \left\{ e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}-il\omega_{cs}\}\phi} \right\} d\phi = \frac{e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega+\nu_s-ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}-il\omega_{cs}\}\phi}}{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega + \nu_s - ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - il\omega_{cs}\}}$$

314 So we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
315 \quad F_{1s} &= -\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}} \sum_{l,m} J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{im\psi} e^{\frac{-1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega + \nu_s - ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel}\}\psi} \\
316 \quad &\cdot \left[i \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} \right. \\
317 \quad &- \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
318 \quad &+ \left. \left\{ f_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\} \right] \\
319 \quad &\cdot \frac{e^{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega + \nu_s - ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - il\omega_{cs}\}\phi}}{\frac{1}{\omega_{cs}}\{i\omega + \nu_s - ik_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - il\omega_{cs}\}}
\end{aligned}$$

320

321 Multiply by $(-i)/(-i)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
322 \quad F_{1s} &= -\sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)}{\{\omega - i\nu_s - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs}\}} e^{i(m-l)\psi} \\
323 \quad &\cdot \left[\frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} \right. \\
324 \quad &+ i \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
325 \quad &- \left. \left\{ f_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

326 Which works out to the final result for the perturbed distribution:

$$\begin{aligned}
327 \quad F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] &= \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)}{\{\omega - i\nu_s - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs}\}} e^{i(m-l)\psi} \\
328 \quad &\cdot \left[i f_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} \right. \\
329 \quad &- i \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
330 \quad &+ \left. i \nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - i \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

331

332 Next, we need to integrate over velocity to obtain the density perturbations:

$$\begin{aligned}
333 \quad n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] &\equiv \int d\vec{v}^3 F_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] \\
334 \quad &= \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_\perp \rho_s) J_l(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - i\nu_s - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs}\}} e^{i(m-l)\psi} \right. \\
335 \quad &\cdot \left[i f_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{k^2 q_s n_0} \cdot \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} \right. \\
336 \quad &- i \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
337 \quad &\left. \left. + i\nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - i \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

338 Separate into like terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
339 \quad n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] &= \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_\perp \rho_s) J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - i\nu_s\}} \cdot [i F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]] \right\} \\
340 \quad &- \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_\perp \rho_s) J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - i\nu_s\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{q_s n_0} \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \frac{\vec{k}}{k^2} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} \right] \right\} \\
341 \quad &- \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_\perp \rho_s) J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - i\nu_s\}} \right. \\
342 \quad &\cdot \left[i \frac{q_s}{m_s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{k}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \right] \left. \right\} \\
343 \quad &+ \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_\perp \rho_s) J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - i\nu_s\}} \left[i\nu_s F_{0s}[\vec{v}] n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] \right. \right. \\
344 \quad &\left. \left. - i \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

345 Factoring out terms independent of velocity,

$$\begin{aligned}
346 \quad n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] &= i \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \cdot F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \right\} \\
347 \quad &- \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{q_s n_0} \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left[\frac{\vec{k}}{k^2} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}[\vec{v}]}{\partial v^*} \right] \right\} \\
348 \quad &- i \frac{q_s}{m_s} \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \right. \\
349 \quad &\cdot \left. \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\vec{k}^3}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \right] \right\} \\
350 \quad &+ \left[iv_s n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] \right. \\
351 \quad &\left. - i \frac{n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]}{n_{0s}} \right] \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

352 We define the same integrals as the linear theory in *Froula et al. (2011)*. Also note that
353 $F_{0s} = n_{0s}f_{0s}$, and $k_{\parallel} \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{l}{\rho_s} \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial v_{\perp}} = \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial \vec{v}^*}$, and the double sum collapses when
354 integrating over ϕ :

$$\begin{aligned}
355 \quad H_s(\omega, \vec{k}) &= \frac{\omega_p^2}{k^2} \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left(\vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial f_{0s}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} \right) \\
356 \quad U_s(\omega, \vec{k}) &= iv_s \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} F_{0s}
\end{aligned}$$

357 This gives (note $F_{0s} = n_0 f_{0s}$ in the H function)

$$\begin{aligned}
358 \quad n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] &= i \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \cdot F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \right\} \\
359 \quad &- \frac{1}{q_s} \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] H_s(\omega, \vec{k}) \\
360 \quad &- i \frac{q_s}{m_s} \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \right. \\
361 \quad &\cdot \left. \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\vec{k}^3}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \right] \right\} \\
362 \quad &+ \left[n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{1}{v_s n_{0s}} n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}] \right] U_s(\omega, \vec{k})
\end{aligned}$$

363
364
365

366 Analogous to H_s , we reorder the integrals in the 2nd order term and define the velocity
 367 integral as

$$368 \quad G_s(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) = \frac{\omega_{ps}^2}{n_0} \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_p(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left(\frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{1s}^{hf}[\nu, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v}]}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} \right)$$

369 So the nonlinear term is rearranged:

$$370 \quad -i \frac{q_s}{m_s} \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \right. \\
 371 \quad \cdot \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\vec{\kappa}^3}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} F_{1s}(\nu, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v}) \right] \Bigg\} \\
 372 \quad = -\frac{i}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{\epsilon_0}{q_s} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_s(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa})$$

373 So the perturbed density is

$$374 \quad n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] = i \int d\vec{v}^3 \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \cdot F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \right\} \\
 375 \quad - \frac{1}{q_s} \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] H_s(\omega, \vec{k}) - \frac{i}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{\epsilon_0}{q_s} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_s(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) \\
 376 \quad + \left[n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] - \frac{1}{v_s} n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}] \right] U_s(\omega, \vec{k})$$

377 We want the t_0 terms together, so recognize that $n_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}] = \int d\vec{v}^3 f_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]$:

$$378 \quad n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] = i \int d\vec{v}^3 F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \left\{ \sum_{l,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} + \frac{i}{v_s} U_s(\omega, \vec{k}) \right\} \\
 379 \quad - \frac{1}{q_s} \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] H_s(\omega, \vec{k}) - \frac{i}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{\epsilon_0}{q_s} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_s(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) \\
 380 \quad + n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] U_s(\omega, \vec{k})$$

381 We will define the intermediate distribution term as

$$382 \quad D_s = \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 F_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \left\{ \sum_l \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s)J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s)e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{(\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s)} + i \frac{U_s(\omega, \vec{k})}{v_s} \right\} \quad (59)$$

383 And suppress the frequency/wavenumber dependence, noting that all terms except the
 384 nonlinear term are evaluated at (ω, k) . The perturbed density is then

$$385 \quad n_{1s} = iD_s - \frac{1}{q_s} \rho_1 H_s - \frac{i}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{\epsilon_0}{q_s} \int d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_s(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) + n_{1s} U_s$$

386 We further shorthand the nonlinear term integrals, defining the operator $\mathcal{F}$ where

$$387 \quad \frac{i\epsilon_0}{(2\pi)^4} \int d\vec{\kappa}^3 \int dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_s(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) = \mathcal{F} E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_s(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa})$$

388 Or suppressing the arguments,

$$389 \quad \frac{i\epsilon_0}{(2\pi)^4} \int d\vec{k}^3 \int dv E_1 G_s(\omega, \vec{k}, v, \vec{k}) = \mathcal{F}E_1 G_s$$

390 Then we have

$$391 \quad n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] = iD_s - \frac{1}{q_s} \rho_1 H_s - \frac{1}{q_s} \mathcal{F}E_1 G_s + n_{1s} U_s$$

392

393 With $\rho_1 = e(n_{1i}[\omega, \vec{k}] - n_{1e}[\omega, \vec{k}])$ we now have our set of electron and ion equations,

$$394 \quad n_{1e}[\omega, \vec{k}] = iD_e + \frac{e}{e} (n_{1i}[\omega, \vec{k}] - n_{1e}[\omega, \vec{k}]) H_e + \frac{1}{e} \mathcal{F}E_1 G_e + n_{1e} U_e \quad (27b)$$

$$395 \quad n_{1i}[\omega, \vec{k}] = iD_i - \frac{e}{e} (n_{1i}[\omega, \vec{k}] - n_{1e}[\omega, \vec{k}]) H_i - \frac{1}{e} \mathcal{F}E_1 G_i + n_{1i} U_i \quad (28b)$$

396 The b designation in these equation numbers is used to say that these are the same
397 as equations (27) and (28) in the main text but written slightly differently.

398 The task is now to solve this system of equations. The resulting algebra is
399 straightforward, but tedious, which is why we simplified things down to shorthand
400 functions (H , G , D) and suppressed their variable dependencies.

401 Since the $\mathcal{G}_s$ terms evaluate fluctuations at high frequencies, the ion fluctuations
402 should be negligible and we will take $\mathcal{G}_i = 0$. Then we have (suppressing all ω, k
403 dependence as we know the nonlinear term is the only one that's different):

$$404 \quad n_{1e} = iD_e + (n_{1i} - n_{1e}) H_e + \frac{1}{e} \mathcal{F}E_1 G_e + n_{1e} U_e$$

$$405 \quad n_{1i} = iD_i - (n_{1i} - n_{1e}) H_i + n_{1i} U_i$$

406 Isolate the density perturbations:

$$407 \quad n_{1e}(1 + H_e - U_e) = iD_e + n_{1i} H_e + \frac{1}{e} \mathcal{F}E_1 G_e$$

$$408 \quad n_{1i}(1 + H_i - U_i) = iD_i + n_{1e} H_i$$

409 Solving for the ion density,

$$410 \quad n_{1i} = \frac{iD_i + n_{1e} H_i}{(1 + H_i - U_i)}$$

411 Putting this into the electron equation,

$$412 \quad n_{1e}(1 + H_e - U_e) = iD_e + \left[\frac{iD_i + n_{1e} H_i}{(1 + H_i - U_i)} \right] H_e + \frac{1}{e} \mathcal{F}E_1 G_e$$

413 Now just solve for n_{1e} :

$$414 \quad n_{1e} \left(1 + H_e - U_e - \frac{H_i H_e}{(1 + H_i - U_i)} \right) = iD_e + \left[\frac{iD_i}{(1 + H_i - U_i)} \right] H_e + \frac{1}{e} \mathcal{F}E_1 G_e$$

415 Define the susceptibilities as

$$416 \quad \chi_s = \frac{H_s}{1 - U_s}$$

417 Then we have

$$418 \quad n_{1e} = \frac{iD_e}{\left(1 + H_e - U_e - \frac{H_i H_e}{(1 + H_i - U_i)}\right)}$$

$$419 \quad + \left[\frac{iD_i}{(1 + H_i - U_i)} \right] \frac{H_e}{\left(1 + H_e - U_e - \frac{H_i H_e}{(1 + H_i - U_i)}\right)}$$

$$420 \quad + \frac{(FE_1 G_e)}{e \left(1 + H_e - U_e - \frac{H_i H_e}{(1 + H_i - U_i)}\right)}$$

421 n_{1e}

$$422 = \frac{iD_e}{(1 - U_e) \left(1 + \frac{H_e}{(1 - U_e)} - \frac{H_i H_e}{(1 - U_e)(1 - U_i) \left(1 + \frac{H_i}{(1 - U_i)}\right)}\right)}$$

$$423 + \left[\frac{iD_i}{(1 - U_i) \left(1 + \frac{H_i}{(1 - U_i)}\right)} \right] \frac{H_e}{(1 - U_e) \left(1 + \frac{H_e}{(1 - U_e)} - \frac{H_i H_e}{(1 - U_e)(1 - U_i) \left(1 + \frac{H_i}{(1 - U_i)}\right)}\right)}$$

$$424 + \frac{(FE_1 G_e)}{e(1 - U_e) \left(1 + \frac{H_e}{(1 - U_e)} - \frac{H_i H_e}{(1 - U_e)(1 - U_i) \left(1 + \frac{H_i}{(1 - U_i)}\right)}\right)}$$

425 Simplify:

$$426 \quad n_{1e} = \frac{iD_e}{(1 - U_e) \left(1 + \chi_e - \frac{\chi_i \chi_e}{(1 + \chi_i)}\right)} + \left[\frac{iD_i}{(1 - U_i)(1 + \chi_i)} \right] \frac{\chi_e}{\left(1 + \chi_e - \frac{\chi_e \chi_i}{(1 + \chi_i)}\right)}$$

$$427 \quad + \frac{(FE_1 G_e)}{e(1 - U_e) \left(1 + \chi_e - \frac{\chi_e \chi_i}{(1 + \chi_i)}\right)}$$

428 Multiply by $(1 + \chi_i)/(1 + \chi_i)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
429 \quad n_{1e} &= \frac{iD_e(1 + \chi_i)}{(1 - U_e)((1 + \chi_e)(1 + \chi_i) - \chi_i\chi_e)} \\
430 \quad &+ \left[\frac{iD_i}{(1 - U_i)(1 + \chi_i)} \right] \frac{\chi_e(1 + \chi_i)}{((1 + \chi_e)(1 + \chi_i) - \chi_i\chi_e)} \\
431 \quad &+ \frac{(1 + \chi_i)(\mathcal{F}E_1G_e)}{e(1 - U_e)((1 + \chi_e)(1 + \chi_i) - \chi_i\chi_e)}
\end{aligned}$$

432 Since $(1 + \chi_e)(1 + \chi_i) - \chi_i\chi_e = 1 + \chi_e + \chi_i = \epsilon$, we have

$$433 \quad n_{1e} = \left(\frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right) \frac{iD_e}{(1 - U_e)} + \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \left[\frac{iD_i}{(1 - U_i)} \right] + \left(\frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right) \frac{(\mathcal{F}E_1G_e)}{e(1 - U_e)}$$

434 We shorthanded the nonlinear term to be

$$435 \quad \frac{i\epsilon_0}{(2\pi)^4} \int d\vec{k}^3 \int dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_s(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) = \mathcal{F}E_1G_s$$

436 So putting this back in,

$$\begin{aligned}
437 \quad n_{1e} &= \left(\frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right) \frac{iD_e}{(1 - U_e)} + \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \left[\frac{iD_i}{(1 - U_i)} \right] \\
438 \quad &+ \left(\frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right) \frac{1}{e(1 - U_e)} \frac{i\epsilon_0}{(2\pi)^4} \int d\vec{k}^3 \int dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_e(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) \\
439 \quad & \hspace{15em} (29)
\end{aligned}$$

440

441 3. Obtaining the Scattering Spectra

442 We now square and ensemble average (See Appendix A) the perturbed density to
443 obtain the scattering spectra (note $\frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} = 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon}$ since $\epsilon = 1 + \chi_e + \chi_i$)

$$\begin{aligned}
444 \quad \langle |n_{1e}|^2 \rangle &= \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_e}{2\nu_e} + \left| \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_i}{2\nu_i} \\
445 \quad &+ \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{e^2 |1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2}{(2\pi)^8} \left(\int d\vec{k}^3 \int dv E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_e(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) \right. \\
446 \quad &\cdot \left. CC \left\{ \int d\vec{k}^3 \int dv \vec{E}_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] \cdot \vec{G}_e(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) \right\} \right) \\
447 \quad & \hspace{15em} (30)
\end{aligned}$$

448 Where we redefine the distribution terms to $M_s = 2\nu_s \left\langle \left| \frac{D_s}{1 - U_s} \right|^2 \right\rangle$.

449 As discussed in the main text, we make the integrals over κ be in spherical
450 coordinates,

$$451 \quad \int d\vec{k}^3 F = 4\pi \int_0^\infty d\kappa \kappa^2 F \quad (32)$$

452 And approximate the frequency ν integration as a Lorentzian so

$$453 \quad \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv F = 2\gamma F \quad (33)$$

$$454 \quad \langle |n_{1e}|^2 \rangle = \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_e}{2\nu_e} + \left| \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_i}{2\nu_i} + \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{e^2 |1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 4\pi \cdot 4\pi \cdot 2\gamma \cdot 2\gamma}{(2\pi)^8}$$

$$455 \quad \cdot \left\langle \int d\kappa \kappa^2 E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_e(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) \right.$$

$$456 \quad \cdot CC \left. \left\{ \int d\kappa \kappa^2 E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_e(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) \right\} \right\rangle$$

$$457 \quad (34)$$

458 In the main text we make the two κ 's equal to each other, and discretize the κ
459 integrations to obtain

$$460 \quad \langle |n_{1e}|^2 \rangle = \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_e}{2\nu_e} + \left| \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_i}{2\nu_i} + \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2}{4\pi^6 e^2}$$

$$461 \quad \cdot \left\langle \sum_{\kappa_i} \Delta\kappa^2 \kappa^4 \left(E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*] G_e(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) \right) \left(\overline{E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]} \cdot \overline{G_e(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa})} \right) \right\rangle$$

462 Combining the complex conjugates,

$$463 \quad \langle |n_{1e}|^2 \rangle = \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_e}{2\nu_e} + \left| \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_i}{2\nu_i} + \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2}{4\pi^6 e^2}$$

$$464 \quad \cdot \left\langle \sum_{\kappa_i} \Delta\kappa^2 \kappa^4 |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 |G_e(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa})|^2 \right\rangle$$

$$465 \quad (35)$$

466 Let us put the G_e back in:

$$467 \quad G_e(\omega, \vec{k}, \nu, \vec{\kappa}) = \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0} \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_p(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_s\}} \left(\frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{1e}^{hf}[v, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v}]}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} \right)$$

$$468 \quad \langle |n_{1e}|^2 \rangle = \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_e}{2\nu_e} + \left| \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_i}{2\nu_i} + \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2}{4\pi^6 e^2} \frac{\omega_{ps}^4}{n_0^2}$$

$$469 \quad \cdot \left\langle \sum_{\kappa_i} \Delta\kappa^2 \kappa^4 \left(|E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \right) \right.$$

$$470 \quad \cdot \left. \left| \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_p(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_s\}} \left(\frac{\vec{k}^*}{k^*} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{1e}^{hf}[v, \vec{\kappa}, \vec{v}]}{\partial \vec{v}^{**}} \right) \right|^2 \right\rangle$$

471 Now put the explicit form of the gradient back in. Also, since we are imposing the
472 perturbed electric field, it does not depend on the ensemble averaging. We then have

$$\begin{aligned}
473 \quad \langle |n_{1e}|^2 \rangle &= \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_e}{2\nu_e} + \left| \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_i}{2\nu_i} + \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2}{4\pi^6 e^2} \frac{\omega_{pe}^4}{n_0^2 k^{*2}} \\
474 \quad &\cdot \sum_{\kappa_i} \Delta \kappa^2 \kappa^4 |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \left\langle \left| \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) J_p(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - i\nu_s\}} \right. \right. \\
475 \quad &\cdot \left. \left. \left(k_\parallel^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_\parallel} + \frac{k_\perp^* l}{k_\perp \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_\perp} \right) f_{1s}^{hf} [v, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \right|^2 \right\rangle
\end{aligned}$$

476 At this point we have all the possible driving wavenumbers κ . Let's pick $\kappa = k_{hf}$,
477 then we have $k^* = k - k_{hf}$ where $k = k_{lf}$ in some contexts. Then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
478 \quad \langle |n_{1e}|^2 \rangle &= \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_e}{2\nu_e} + \left| \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{M_i}{2\nu_i} + \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2}{4\pi^6 e^2} \frac{\omega_{pe}^4}{n_0^2 k^{*2}} \gamma^2 [\omega_{hf}, k_{hf}] \\
479 \quad &\cdot \sum_{all\ k_{hf}} \Delta k_{hf}^2 k_{hf}^4 |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \left\langle \left| \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) J_p(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - i\nu_s\}} \right. \right. \\
480 \quad &\cdot \left. \left. \left(k_\parallel^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_\parallel} + \frac{k_\perp^* l}{k_\perp \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_\perp} \right) f_{1s}^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] \right|^2 \right\rangle, \\
481 \quad & \tag{36}
\end{aligned}$$

482 where we previously defined the shifted frequencies and wavenumbers as

$$483 \quad \omega^* = \omega - \omega_{hf}, \tag{37}$$

$$484 \quad \vec{k}^* = \vec{k} - \vec{k}_{hf}. \tag{38}$$

485 with $(\omega, \vec{k})$ being low-frequency values.

486 Equation 36 is the final solution for the electron density fluctuations. It includes
487 contributions from all possible driving wavenumbers, k_{hf} . Since the integration over k_{hf}
488 was discretized, we can either search for the contributions from a single driving source or
489 add up the contributions from multiple sources to obtain a realistic result of the Upper-
490 Hybrid mode being excited across a wide range of wavenumbers.

491 To obtain the scattering power, equation 18 is combined with equation 36:

$$\begin{aligned}
492 \quad S(\omega, \vec{k}) &= \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 M_e + \left| \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 M_i \\
493 \quad &+ \sum_{all\ k_{hf}} \nu_e \left| 1 - \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 [\omega_{hf}, k_{hf}] \Delta k_{hf}^2}{2\pi^6 e^2} \frac{\omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{n_0^2 k^{*2}} \\
494 \quad &\cdot |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \cdot \langle T \rangle, \\
495 \quad & \tag{39}
\end{aligned}$$

496 and the summation over all k_{hf} can be dropped at any point. The ensemble average term
 497 in equation 39 is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 498 \quad \langle T \rangle &\equiv \frac{1}{N} \left\langle \left| \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_p(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \right. \right. \\
 499 \quad &\quad \cdot \left. \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* l}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) f_{1e}^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] \right|^2 \Bigg\rangle \\
 500 & \tag{40}
 \end{aligned}$$

501 The remaining task is to evaluate equation 40.

502

503 4. High Frequency Solution

504 The solution for the scattering spectra requires the high frequency distribution f_{1s}^{hf}
 505 in equation (40). (Somewhere F_{1e}^{hf} changed to f_{1e}^{hf} , at this point the notational distinction
 506 is not important, as we never normalize the perturbed distribution.)

507 We further took the assumption that $G_i = 0$ at high frequencies. We therefore
 508 need to find f_{1e}^{hf} . This was (sort of) done in the *Longley et al. (2020)*, and we can bring
 509 those results here. The perturbed distribution of a magnetized, BGK collisional plasma is
 510 (note: this is effectively the linear version of equation 17):

$$\begin{aligned}
 511 \quad f_{1s}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) &= - \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_p(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left[if_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] + \frac{4\pi q}{k^2 m_s} \rho_1[\omega, \vec{k}] \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} \right. \\
 512 \quad &\quad \left. + iv_s n_{1s}[\omega, \vec{k}] f_{0s} - in_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}] f_{0s} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

513 We consider the ion response negligible at high frequencies, and therefore we have $\rho_1 =$
 514 $-en_{1e} = -e \int d\vec{v} f_{1e}$, so then (note, we're suppressing the double sum over p, l and will
 515 reinstate it later)

$$\begin{aligned}
 516 \quad f_{1s}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) &= - \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_{\perp}\rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left[if_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] \right. \\
 517 \quad &\quad \left. + \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k^2} \left(\int d\vec{v} f_{1e}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \right) \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + iv_s \left(\int d\vec{v} f_{1e}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \right) f_{0s} \right. \\
 518 \quad &\quad \left. - in_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}] f_{0s} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

519 Pulling all of the f_{1s} ($=f_{1e}$) dependence onto the LHS, and noting that $\frac{4\pi e^2 n_0}{m_e} = \omega_{pe}^2$ in
 520 cgs,

$$\begin{aligned}
521 \quad & f_{1s}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) + \left(\int d\vec{v} f_{1e}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \right) \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k^2} \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} \right. \\
522 \quad & \left. + iv_s f_{0s} \right] \\
523 \quad & = - \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} [if_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - in_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]f_{0s}]
\end{aligned}$$

524 Since the integral of f_{1e} is isolated, we can obtain it by integrating equation (61) over
525 velocity

$$\begin{aligned}
526 \quad & \int d\vec{v} f_{1s}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
527 \quad & + \left(\int d\vec{v} f_{1e}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \right) \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k^2} \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} \right. \right. \\
528 \quad & \left. \left. + iv_s f_{0s} \right] \right\} \\
529 \quad & = - \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} [if_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - in_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]f_{0s}] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

530 Simplifying,

$$\begin{aligned}
531 \quad & \left(\int d\vec{v} f_{1e}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \right) \left[1 + \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k^2} \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + iv_s f_{0s} \right] \right\} \right] \\
532 \quad & = - \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} [if_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - in_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]f_{0s}] \right\} \\
533 \quad & \int d\vec{v} f_{1e}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) \\
534 \quad & = - \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} [if_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - in_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]f_{0s}] \right\} \\
535 \quad & \cdot \left[1 + \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k^2} \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + iv_s f_{0s} \right] \right\} \right]^{-1}
\end{aligned}$$

536 Putting this into equation (61), we find

$$\begin{aligned}
537 \quad f_{1s}^{hf}(\omega, \vec{k}, \vec{v}) &= \left(\int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} [if_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - in_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]f_{0s}] \right\} \right. \\
538 \quad &\cdot \left. \left[1 + \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k^2} \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + iv_s f_{0s} \right] \right\} \right]^{-1} \right) \\
539 \quad &\cdot \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k^2} \vec{k} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0s}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + iv_s f_{0s} \right] \\
540 \quad &- \sum_l \frac{J_l^2(k_\perp \rho_s)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - l\omega_{cs} - iv_s\}} [if_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] - in_{1s}[t_0, \vec{k}]f_{0s}]
\end{aligned}$$

541 Note that the term in blue, $\int d\vec{v} f_{1e} = n_{1e}$ has no velocity dependence as the integration
542 is effectively over a dummy variable. Also note that the integrals in the n_{1e} term are
543 related to the integrals previously dealt with, though we will need to make those
544 substitutions in a manner that allows for a 0th order distribution that includes
545 suprathermal electrons.

546 We can shorthand the leading factors, and note that we need f_{1s}^{hf} evaluated at
547 $\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}$. The double sum is also reinstated, and we finally optain

$$\begin{aligned}
548 \quad f_{1e}^{hf}(\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}) &= \left(\frac{D_1^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) \\
549 \quad &\cdot \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) J_p(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k_{hf}^2} \vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0e}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + iv_e f_{0e} \right] \\
550 \quad &- \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) J_p(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] - in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}]f_{0e}], \\
551 \quad & \\
552 \quad & \tag{41}
\end{aligned}$$

553 where the functions in the leading factor are

$$554 \quad H_1^{hf} = \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) J_p(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k_{hf}^2} \vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0e}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + iv_e f_{0e} \right] \right\}, \tag{42}$$

$$555 \quad D_1^{hf} = \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) J_p(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] - in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}]f_{0e}] \right\}. \tag{43}$$

556

557

558

559

560 **5. Evaluating the Ensemble Average**

561 Putting the perturbed distribution into the scattering equation,

$$\begin{aligned}
562 \quad \langle |n_{1e}|^2 \rangle &= \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \langle |M_e|^2 \rangle + \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \langle |M_i|^2 \rangle \\
563 \quad &+ \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta k^2}{4\pi^6 e^2} \frac{\omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \\
564 \quad &\cdot \left\langle \left| \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{\perp} \rho_s) J_p(k_{\perp} \rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - i\nu_s\}} \right. \right. \\
565 \quad &\cdot \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* l}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \left\{ \left(\frac{D_1^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) \right. \\
566 \quad &\cdot \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_s) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_s) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k_{hf}^2} \vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0e}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + i\nu_e f_{0e} \right] \\
567 \quad &- \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_s) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_s) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} [if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] \\
568 \quad &\left. \left. \left. - in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}] f_{0e} \right] \right\} \right|^2 \Bigg\rangle
\end{aligned}$$

569 Looking at this, the integral over v in the first G_e term is closed form and independent of
570 initial state for part of the integrand. The dependence on the initial state comes from the
571 D_1^{hf} term, which is independent of v and can be pulled out of the integral, and the second
572 summation over l . Note that D^{hf} , H^{hf} , and U^{hf} are all evaluated at $\omega = \omega_{hf}$ and $\vec{k} =$
573 $\vec{k}_{hf}$, and $U_m^{*hf} \equiv U_m^{hf}[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]$. We can define the closed form integral

$$\begin{aligned}
574 \quad Y^{hf} &= \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_s) J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_s) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* n}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
575 \quad &\cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k_{hf}^2} \vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0e}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + i\nu_e f_{0e} \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

576 Which gives

$$\begin{aligned}
577 \quad \langle |n_{1e}|^2 \rangle &= \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \langle |M_e|^2 \rangle + \frac{\chi_e}{\epsilon} \langle |M_i|^2 \rangle \\
578 \quad &+ \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2 \omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{4\pi^6 e^2 n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \\
579 \quad &\cdot \left\| \left(\frac{D_1^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) Y^{hf} \right. \\
580 \quad &- \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{\perp} \rho_s) J_p(k_{\perp} \rho_s) e^{i(m-l)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{cs} - i\nu_s\}} \cdot \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* l}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
581 \quad &\cdot \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_s) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_s) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} [if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] \\
582 \quad &- in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}] f_{0e}] \left. \right\|^2
\end{aligned}$$

583 The definitions of velocity integrals in G_e are not entirely accurate, and instead shorthand
584 the Klimontovich formalism. The Klimontovich formalism really just substitutes $\int d\vec{v} \rightarrow$
585 $\sum_{\nu} d\vec{v}$ as a discretization of the velocity, and $F_{1s}[t, \vec{r}, \vec{v}] = \sum_j^{N_s} \delta[\vec{r} - \vec{r}_j(t)] \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)]$
586 for the formal definition of the particle distribution. Of particular use is the equivalence

$$587 \quad \int d\vec{v} \frac{f_{1e}(t_0, \vec{k}, \vec{v})}{(\omega - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{v} - i\gamma)} = \sum_j^N \frac{\exp(i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0))}{(\omega - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)}$$

588 The D integral evaluates in the Klimontovich formalism to

$$589 \quad D_1^{hf} = \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} [if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] - in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}] f_{0e}] \right\}$$

$$590 \quad D_1^{hf} = i \sum_j^N \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) e^{i(l-p)\phi(0)} \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0))}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{j,\parallel}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \\
591 \quad - i \left\{ \int d\vec{v} \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) e^{i(l-p)\phi} f_{0e}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \right\} \sum_j^N \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0))$$

$$592 \quad D_1^{hf} = i \sum_j^N \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)) \left[\sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) e^{i(l-p)\phi(0)}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{j,\parallel}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \right. \\
593 \quad \left. - \sum_{l,p} \int d\vec{v} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) e^{i(l-p)\phi} f_{0e}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \right]$$

594 The remaining integral over velocity is the same as U_e^{hf}/iv_e in equation 75, so we have

$$595 \quad D_1^{hf} = i \sum_j^N \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)) \left[\sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(l-p)\phi(0)}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{j,\parallel}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} - \frac{1}{iv_e} U_e^{hf}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right]$$

596 The last integral in the scattering equation is worked out in Appendix C. The result is

$$597 \quad \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \frac{n}{\rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right)$$

$$598 \quad \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]] \right.$$

$$599 \quad \left. - in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}]F_{0e} \right\}$$

$$600 \quad = - \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}$$

$$601 \quad \cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right.$$

$$602 \quad \left. + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp,j}(0)} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right.$$

$$603 \quad \cdot [J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)))$$

$$604 \quad \left. + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))(J_{m-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))) \right]$$

$$605 \quad - \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} Z^{hf}$$

$$606 \quad \tag{84}$$

607 With

$$608 \quad Z^{hf} = \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \frac{n}{\rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right)$$

$$609 \quad \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [if_{0e}] \right\}$$

$$610 \quad \tag{85}$$

611 Let us make some substitutions so the upcoming equation doesn't kill a page:

$$\begin{aligned}
612 \quad J_j &= i \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l^j(k_{hf}) J_p^j(k_{hf}) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel,j}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
613 \quad &\cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n^j(k) J_m^j(k) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right. \\
614 \quad &+ \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp,j}(0)} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \\
615 \quad &\cdot \left[J_m^j(k_{\perp}) (J_{n-1}^j(k_{\perp}) - J_{n+1}^j(k_{\perp})) + J_n^j(k_{\perp}) (J_{m-1}^j(k_{\perp}) - J_{m+1}^j(k_{\perp})) \right] \left. \right\} \\
616 \quad & \\
617 \quad \mathcal{H}_j &= i \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) e^{i(l-p)\phi_j(0)}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{j,\parallel}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}}
\end{aligned}$$

618 Then we start working on the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
619 \quad S_{NL} &= \left| \frac{1 + \chi i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2 \omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{4\pi^6 e^2 n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \\
620 \quad &\cdot \left\| \left\{ \left(\frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) \left(i \sum_j^N \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)) \right. \right. \right. \\
621 \quad &\cdot \left. \left[\sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) e^{i(l-p)\phi(0)}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{j,\parallel}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} - \frac{1}{iv_e} U_e^{hf}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right] \right\} \right. \\
622 \quad &+ \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{j,\parallel}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
623 \quad &\cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right. \\
624 \quad &+ \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp,j}(0)} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \\
625 \quad &\cdot \left[J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0))) \right. \\
626 \quad &+ \left. \left. J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) (J_{m-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0))) \right] \right\} \\
627 \quad &+ \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} Z^{hf} \left. \right\|^2
\end{aligned}$$

628 Factor out the leading particle sum:

$$\begin{aligned}
629 \quad & S_{NL} \\
630 \quad & = \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2}{4\pi^6 e^2} \frac{\omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \\
631 \quad & \cdot \left\langle \left| \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \right|^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{iY^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) \left(\sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) e^{i(l-p)\phi(0)}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{j,\parallel}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \right. \right. \\
632 \quad & \left. \left. \left. - \frac{1}{iv_e} U_e^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) + \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_j(0)) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{j,\parallel}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \right. \\
633 \quad & \cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{j,\parallel}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right. \\
634 \quad & \left. + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp,j}(0)} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{j,\parallel}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
635 \quad & \cdot \left[J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0))) \right. \\
636 \quad & \left. \left. + J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) (J_{m-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0)) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_j(0))) \right] \right\} + Z^{hf} \left. \right\}^2
\end{aligned}$$

637

638 Substitute the $\mathcal{J}$ and $\mathcal{H}$ shorthands,

$$\begin{aligned}
639 \quad & S_{NL} = \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2}{4\pi^6 e^2} \frac{\omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \\
640 \quad & \cdot \left\langle \left| \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \right|^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) \left(\mathcal{H}_j - \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) + \mathcal{J}_j \right. \right. \\
641 \quad & \left. \left. + Z^{hf} \right\} \right|^2
\end{aligned}$$

642 Note that the script functions carry initial time dependence, but the Y , U , H , and Z
643 functions do not. We now square this:

$$\begin{aligned}
644 \quad S_{NL} &= \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2}{4\pi^6 e^2} \frac{\omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \\
645 &\cdot \left\langle \left[\sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \sum_{j'}^N e^{-i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_{j'}(0)} \right] \right. \\
646 &\cdot \left[\left(\frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) \left(\mathcal{H}_j - \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) + \mathcal{J}_j + Z^{hf} \right] \\
647 &\cdot \left. \left[\overline{\left(\frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right)} \left(\overline{\mathcal{H}_j'} - \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{U_e^{hf}}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) + \overline{\mathcal{J}_j'} + \overline{Z^{hf}} \right] \right\rangle
\end{aligned}$$

648 The ' on $\overline{\mathcal{J}_j'}$ is there simply to note the summation indices are different than on a
649 neighboring $\mathcal{J}$. Multiplying out, noting that $\mathcal{H}_j$ and $\overline{\mathcal{H}_j'}$ are not complex conjugates
650 because of the different summation indices,

$$\begin{aligned}
651 \quad S_{NL} &= \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2}{4\pi^6 e^2} \frac{\omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \\
652 &\cdot \left\langle \left[\sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \sum_{j'}^N e^{-i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_{j'}(0)} \right] \right. \\
653 &\cdot \left[\left| \frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right|^2 \left(\mathcal{H}_j \overline{\mathcal{H}_j'} - \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{\mathcal{H}_j'} U_e^{hf}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] - \frac{1}{v_e} \mathcal{H}_j \overline{U_e^{hf}}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) \right. \\
654 &+ \frac{1}{v_e^2} |U_e^{hf}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}]|^2 \left. \right) + \mathcal{J}_j \left(\frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) \left(\overline{\mathcal{H}_j'} - \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{U_e^{hf}}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) \\
655 &+ Z^{hf} \left(\frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) \left(\overline{\mathcal{H}_j'} - \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{U_e^{hf}}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) \\
656 &+ \overline{\mathcal{J}_j'} \left(\frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) \left(\mathcal{H}_j - \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) \\
657 &+ \overline{Z^{hf}} \left(\frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \right) \left(\mathcal{H}_j - \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf}[\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) + \mathcal{J}_j \overline{\mathcal{J}_j'} + |Z^{hf}|^2 + \mathcal{J}_j \overline{Z^{hf}} \\
658 &\left. \left. + \overline{\mathcal{J}_j'} Z^{hf} \right] \right\rangle
\end{aligned}$$

659 To shorthand some, let's define (Note: this was regrettable)

$$660 \quad Y_{H1}^{hf} = \frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
661 \quad S_{NL} &= \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2 \omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{4\pi^6 e^2 n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \\
662 &\cdot \left\langle \left[\sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \sum_{j'}^N e^{-i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_{j'}(0)} \right] \right. \\
663 &\cdot \left[|Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \left(\mathcal{H}_j \bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' - \frac{1}{v_e} \bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' U_e^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] - \frac{1}{v_e} \mathcal{H}_j \bar{U}_e^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right. \right. \\
664 &+ \left. \left. \frac{1}{v_e^2} |U_e^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}]|^2 \right) + \mathcal{J}_j \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \left(\bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' - \frac{1}{v_e} \bar{U}_e^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) \right. \\
665 &+ Z^{hf} \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \left(\bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' - \frac{1}{v_e} \bar{U}_e^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) + \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' Y_{H1}^{hf} \left(\mathcal{H}_j - \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) \\
666 &+ \bar{Z}^{hf} Y_{H1}^{hf} \left(\mathcal{H}_j - \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf} [\omega_{hf}, \vec{k}_{hf}] \right) + \mathcal{J}_j \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' + |Z^{hf}|^2 + \mathcal{J}_j \bar{Z}^{hf} \\
667 &\left. \left. + \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' Z^{hf} \right] \right\rangle
\end{aligned}$$

668 Do some grouping by almost conjugate terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
669 \quad S_{NL} &= \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2 \omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{4\pi^6 e^2 n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \\
670 &\cdot \left\langle \left[\sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \sum_{j'}^N e^{-i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_{j'}(0)} \right] \right. \\
671 &\cdot \left[\mathcal{J}_j \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' + \left[\bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' \mathcal{J}_j \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} + \mathcal{H}_j \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' Y_{H1}^{hf} \right] + |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \mathcal{H}_j \bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' \right. \\
672 &+ \left[\mathcal{J}_j \left(\bar{Z}^{hf} - \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{v_e} \bar{U}_e^{hf} \right) + \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' \left(Z^{hf} - Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf} \right) \right] \\
673 &+ \left(\mathcal{H}_j \left(\bar{Z}^{hf} Y_{H1}^{hf} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \bar{U}_e^{hf} \right) + \bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' \left(Z^{hf} \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right) \\
674 &+ \left. \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{v_e} Z^{hf} \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \bar{U}_e^{hf} + \frac{1}{v_e} \bar{Z}^{hf} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) + |Z^{hf}|^2 + \frac{1}{v_e^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 |U_e^{hf}|^2 \right\} \right\rangle
\end{aligned}$$

675 Note the last term in $\{ \}$ does not depend on time.

676 We now apply the ensemble average as it's described in Appendix A. If $j \neq j'$
677 then an exponential factor is present and ensemble averages to 0. Therefore only the $j =$
678 j' terms survive the double sum. Loosely, we then substitute

$$679 \quad \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \sum_{j'}^N e^{-i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_{j'}(0)} X = N \int dv f_0(v) X$$

680 Where X is all the other stuff, so we have

$$\begin{aligned}
681 \quad S_{NL} &= N \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2 \omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{4\pi^6 e^2 n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \\
682 \quad &\cdot \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[\mathcal{J}_j \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' + \left[\bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' \mathcal{J}_j \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} + \mathcal{H}_j \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' Y_{H1}^{hf} \right] + |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \mathcal{H}_j \bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' \right. \\
683 \quad &+ \left[\mathcal{J}_j \left(\bar{Z}^{hf} - \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{v_e} \bar{U}_e^{hf} \right) + \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' \left(Z^{hf} - Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf} \right) \right] \\
684 \quad &+ \left(\mathcal{H}_j \left(\bar{Z}^{hf} Y_{H1}^{hf} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \bar{U}_e^{hf} \right) + \bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' \left(Z^{hf} \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right) \\
685 \quad &+ \left. \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{v_e} Z^{hf} \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \bar{U}_e^{hf} + \frac{1}{v_e} \bar{Z}^{hf} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) + |Z^{hf}|^2 + \frac{1}{v_e^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 |U_e^{hf}|^2 \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

686 Note that $\mathcal{G}$, $\mathcal{H}$, and $\mathcal{J}$ no longer need particle sum indices (but we keep the ‘ notation to
687 emphasize the Bessel summations are over different indices)

688 Let’s choose the shorthand function $\langle T \rangle$, where we have

$$689 \quad S_{NL} = \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2 \omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{4\pi^6 e^2 n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \cdot \langle T \rangle$$

690 In full, this defines

$$\begin{aligned}
691 \quad \langle T \rangle &= N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[\mathcal{J}_j \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' + \left[\bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' \mathcal{J}_j \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} + \mathcal{H}_j \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' Y_{H1}^{hf} \right] + |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \mathcal{H}_j \bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' \right. \\
692 \quad &+ \left[\mathcal{J}_j \left(\bar{Z}^{hf} - \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{v_e} \bar{U}_e^{hf} \right) + \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' \left(Z^{hf} - Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf} \right) \right] \\
693 \quad &+ \left(\mathcal{H}_j \left(\bar{Z}^{hf} Y_{H1}^{hf} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \bar{U}_e^{hf} \right) + \bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' \left(Z^{hf} \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right) \\
694 \quad &+ \left. \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{v_e} Z^{hf} \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \bar{U}_e^{hf} + \frac{1}{v_e} \bar{Z}^{hf} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) + |Z^{hf}|^2 + \frac{1}{v_e^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 |U_e^{hf}|^2 \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

695 It is useful to break this up based on how $\mathcal{J}$ and $\mathcal{H}$ are present, as those dictate the poles
696 of the integrand. We define

$$697 \quad \langle T \rangle = \langle T \rangle_a + \langle T \rangle_b + \langle T \rangle_c + \langle T \rangle_d + \langle T \rangle_e + \langle T \rangle_f$$

698 Where we have

$$699 \quad \langle T \rangle_a = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \mathcal{J}_j \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j'$$

$$700 \quad \langle T \rangle_b = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[\bar{\mathcal{H}}_j' \mathcal{J}_j \bar{Y}_{H1}^{hf} + \mathcal{H}_j \bar{\mathcal{J}}_j' Y_{H1}^{hf} \right]$$

$$701 \quad \langle T \rangle_c = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \mathcal{H}_j \bar{\mathcal{H}}_j'$$

$$\begin{aligned}
702 \quad \langle T \rangle_d &= N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[\mathcal{J}_j \left(\overline{Z}^{hf} - \overline{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{U}_e^{hf} \right) + \overline{\mathcal{J}}_j' \left(Z^{hf} - Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf} \right) \right] \\
703 \quad \langle T \rangle_e &= N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[\mathcal{H}_j \left(\overline{Z}^{hf} Y_{H1}^{hf} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \overline{U}_e^{hf} \right) + \overline{\mathcal{H}}_j' \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y}_{H1}^{hf} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right] \\
704 \quad \langle T \rangle_f &= N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{v_e} Z^{hf} \overline{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \overline{U}_e^{hf} + \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{Z}^{hf} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) + |Z^{hf}|^2 + \frac{1}{v_e^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 |U_e^{hf}|^2 \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

705 Where we have defined the following functions:

$$\begin{aligned}
706 \quad \mathcal{H}_j &= i \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - i v_e\}} \\
707 \quad \mathcal{J}_j &= i \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - i v_e\}} \right\} \\
708 \quad &\cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - i v_e\}^2} \right. \\
709 \quad &\left. + \frac{n k_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - i v_e\}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

710 Where we have made the substitution

$$\begin{aligned}
711 \quad B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) &= J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \\
712 \quad &+ J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) (J_{m-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))
\end{aligned}$$

713 With the underbar denoting which summation index is in the denominator of the whole
714 term.

715 The functions not dependent on velocity are

$$\begin{aligned}
716 \quad Z^{hf} &= \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - i v_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* n}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
717 \quad &\cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i v_e\}} [if_{0e}] \right\} \\
718 \quad Y_{H1}^{hf} &= \frac{1}{1 + H_1^{hf}} \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_s) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_s) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - i v_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* n}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
719 \quad &\cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i v_e\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k_{hf}^2} \vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0e}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + i v_e f_{0e} \right] \right\} \\
720 \quad U_s^{hf}[\omega, \vec{k}] &= i v_s \sum_l \int d\vec{v}^3 \frac{J_l^2 \left(k_{\perp} \frac{v_{\perp}}{\Omega_c} \right)}{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\Omega_c - i v_s} f_{0s}(v)
\end{aligned}$$

$$H_1^{hf} = \int d\vec{v} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_\perp \rho_s) J_p(k_\perp \rho_s) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \left[\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k_{hf}^2} \vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \frac{\partial F_{0e}}{\partial \vec{v}^*} + i\nu_e f_{0e} \right] \right\}$$

722

723 6. Simplifying $\langle T \rangle$

724 We will evaluate the $\langle T \rangle_f$ terms in order of easiest (f) to hardest (a).

725 6.1 Tf Term

726 We have

$$727 \langle T \rangle_f = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{v_e} Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \overline{U_e^{hf}} + \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{Z^{hf}} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) + |Z^{hf}|^2 + \frac{1}{v_e^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 |U_e^{hf}|^2 \right\}$$

728 Since the Z , Y , H , and U functions are already integrated over velocity, and therefore
729 independent of it, we can factor those terms out of the integral and obtain

$$730 \langle T \rangle_f = N \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{v_e} Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \overline{U_e^{hf}} + \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{Z^{hf}} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) + |Z^{hf}|^2 + \frac{1}{v_e^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 |U_e^{hf}|^2 \right\} \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v})$$

731 By definition, this integral is equal to 1, and we will not split it into thermal and
732 photoelectron components because the integral is exactly 1.

$$733 \langle T \rangle_f = N \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{v_e} Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \overline{U_e^{hf}} + \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{Z^{hf}} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) + |Z^{hf}|^2 + \frac{1}{v_e^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 |U_e^{hf}|^2 \right\}$$

734 The scattered power is defined as

$$735 S(\omega, \vec{k}) = \frac{2\nu_e}{N} \langle |n_{1e}(\omega, \vec{k})|^2 \rangle$$

736 In the collisional form the limit $\gamma \rightarrow 0$ is not needed, so we can trivially calculate $S(\omega, \vec{k})$
737 by multiplying every term in $\langle T \rangle$ by a factor of $2\nu_e/N$. For notational simplicity, we
738 therefore define T' terms as

$$739 \langle T' \rangle = \frac{2\nu_e}{N} \langle T \rangle$$

740 We then obtain

$$741 \langle T' \rangle_f = 2 \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \overline{U_e^{hf}} + \overline{Z^{hf}} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) + 2\nu_e |Z^{hf}|^2 + \frac{2}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 |U_e^{hf}|^2$$

742 The first term can be simplified:

$$743 \langle T' \rangle_f = 4\text{Re} \left[Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \overline{U_e^{hf}} \right] + 2\nu_e |Z^{hf}|^2 + \frac{2}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 |U_e^{hf}|^2$$

744 6.2 Te Term

745 Next we work out the term

$$746 \quad \langle T \rangle_e = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[\mathcal{H}_j \left(\overline{Z^{hf}} Y_{H1}^{hf} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \overline{U_e^{hf}} \right) + \overline{\mathcal{H}}_j' \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right]$$

747 The terms in parentheses are complex conjugates and independent of velocity. To shorten
748 the equations, we will define for now

$$749 \quad C = \left(\overline{Z^{hf}} Y_{H1}^{hf} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \overline{U_e^{hf}} \right)$$

750 Then we have

$$751 \quad \langle T \rangle_e = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) [\mathcal{H}_j C + \overline{\mathcal{H}}_j' \overline{C}]$$

752 We substitute the $\mathcal{H}$ function which was defined as

$$753 \quad \mathcal{H}_j = i \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}}$$

754 So we have

$$755 \quad \langle T \rangle_e = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[Ci \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\ 756 \quad \left. - \overline{C} i \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{-i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right]$$

757 Putting the integral in cylindrical coordinates,

$$758 \quad \langle T \rangle_e = N \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} d\phi v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \left[Ci \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\ 759 \quad \left. - \overline{C} i \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e(0)) e^{-i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right]$$

760 The angular integral can be isolated:

$$761 \quad \langle T \rangle_e = N \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \left[Ci \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi e^{i(x-y)\phi} \right. \\ 762 \quad \left. - \overline{C} i \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi e^{i(x-y)\phi} \right]$$

763 The integral $\int_0^{2\pi} d\phi e^{i(l-p)\phi}$ evaluates to 2π if $l = p$, and evaluates to 0 if $l \neq p$.

764 Therefore, we have only the diagonal terms of the double summation surviving.

765 $\langle T \rangle_e = 2\pi N \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \left[Ci \sum_x \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right.$

766 $\left. - \bar{C}i \sum_x \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right]$

767 The denominators are simplified to

768 $\langle T \rangle_e = \frac{2\pi N}{k_{hf,\parallel}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \left[-Ci \sum_x \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\left\{v_{\parallel} - \frac{\omega_{hf} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}}\right\}} \right.$

769 $\left. + \bar{C}i \sum_x \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\left\{v_{\parallel} - \frac{\omega_{hf} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}}\right\}} \right]$

770 We therefore define the resonance as

771
$$y_x^{hf} = \frac{\omega_{hf} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}}$$

772 And we obtain

773 $\langle T \rangle_e = \frac{2\pi N}{k_{hf,\parallel}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \left[-Ci \sum_x \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} + \bar{C}i \sum_x \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}} \right]$

774 We have two options at this point. First, we can evaluate the $v_{\parallel}$ integral using the
 775 modified Plemelj theorem. This has caused some issues before though, especially when
 776 the denominators have unmatched poles (such as the case here) that lead to principle
 777 value integrals. The second option is to do a straight numerical integration of these
 778 functions. This leads to higher accuracy over principle value integrations, at the cost of
 779 more computing time. We take this second option for the accuracy, also noting that a
 780 straight integration of $v_{\parallel}$ from $-\infty$ to ∞ means that $v_{\parallel}$ is always real valued in evaluating
 781 the above equation, so the two terms are complex conjugates (note that this is not the case
 782 when evaluating $v_{\parallel}$ along a complex contour). Then we can simplify this to

783 $\langle T \rangle_e = \frac{4\pi N}{k_{hf,\parallel}} \text{Re} \left[i \left(Z^{hf} Y_{H1}^{hf} \right. \right.$

784 $\left. - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}} \left. \right]$

785 We can now multiply by $2v_e/N$ to get the term in the scattering power:

786 $\langle T' \rangle_e = \frac{8\pi v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}} \text{Re} \left[i \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \right. \right.$

787 $\left. \left. - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \right]$

788 We want to evaluate this with the distribution

789
$$f_{0e} = f_{0m} + \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} f_{0h}$$

790 Where the thermal density is much greater than the photoelectron density: $n_{0m} \gg n_{0h}$.

791 We will take the thermal distribution to be a Maxwellian, which we write in $v_{\perp}$ and $v_{\parallel}$

792 coordinates

793
$$f_{0m} = \frac{1}{(\pi v_{th}^2)^{3/2}} \exp \left[-\frac{(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

794 We keep the photoelectron distribution undefined and evaluate it numerically. We break

795 $\langle T' \rangle_f$ into thermal and photoelectron terms based on the linearity of f_{0e} , with $\langle T' \rangle_f =$

796 $\langle T' \rangle_f^{th} + \langle T' \rangle_f^{ph}$:

797 $\langle T' \rangle_e^{th}$

798 $= \frac{8\pi v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}} \text{Re} \left[i \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right.$

799 $\left. \cdot \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \frac{1}{(\pi v_{th}^2)^{3/2}} \exp \left[-\frac{(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]$

800 $\langle T' \rangle_e^{ph} = \frac{8\pi v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel} n_{0m}} \text{Re} \left[i \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right.$

801 $\left. \cdot \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \right]$

802 Simplify to obtain the result:

803 $\langle T' \rangle_e^{th} = \frac{8v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}} \text{Re} \left[i \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right.$

804 $\left. \cdot \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]$

$$\begin{aligned}
805 \quad \langle T' \rangle_e^{ph} &= \frac{8\pi v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel} n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[i \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right. \\
806 \quad &\left. \cdot \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

807

808 6.3 Td Term

809 The next term to work on is

$$810 \quad \langle T \rangle_a = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[\mathcal{J}_j \left(\overline{Z}^{hf} - \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{U_e^{hf}} \right) + \overline{\mathcal{J}}_j' \left(Z^{hf} - Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{v_e} U_e^{hf} \right) \right]$$

811 Let's again use a placeholder

$$812 \quad C = \overline{Z}^{hf} - \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \frac{1}{v_e} \overline{U_e^{hf}}$$

813 And we have

$$\begin{aligned}
814 \quad \mathcal{J}_j &= i \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
815 \quad &\cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_e) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right. \\
816 \quad &\left. + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
817 \quad B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) &= J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \\
818 \quad &+ J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{m-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))
\end{aligned}$$

819 Putting this in, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
820 \quad \langle T \rangle_d &= N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[iC \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
821 \quad &\cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right. \\
822 \quad &\left. \left. + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
823 \quad &- \bar{C}i \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{-i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \\
824 \quad &\cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{-i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right. \\
825 \quad &\left. \left. + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) e^{-i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

826 The form of the integrals suggests we break this into two separate terms: $\langle T \rangle_d = \langle T \rangle_d^{\parallel} +$
827 $\langle T \rangle_d^{\perp}$

$$\begin{aligned}
828 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^{\parallel} &= k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[iC \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
829 \quad &\cdot \left\{ \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\} \\
830 \quad &- \bar{C}i \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{-i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \\
831 \quad &\cdot \left\{ \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{-i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\} \left. \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
832 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\perp &= N \frac{k_\perp^*}{2} \int d\vec{v}^3 \frac{1}{v_\perp} f_0(\vec{v}) \left[iC \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
833 \quad &\quad \cdot \left. \left\{ \sum_{n,m} \frac{n B(k_\perp, \underline{n}, m) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
834 \quad &\quad - \bar{C}i \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf}\rho_e) e^{-i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \\
835 \quad &\quad \cdot \left. \left\{ \sum_{n,m} \frac{n B(k_\perp, \underline{n}, m) e^{-i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

836 Put each integral into cylindrical coordinates,

$$\begin{aligned}
837 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\parallel &= k_\parallel^* k_\parallel N \sum_{x,y,n,m} \int dv_\perp dv_\parallel v_\perp f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel) \\
838 \quad &\quad \cdot \left[iC \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_n(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_\perp\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\} \right. \\
839 \quad &\quad \cdot \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi e^{i(x-y+n-m)\phi} \\
840 \quad &\quad - \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \frac{J_n(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_\perp\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\} \\
841 \quad &\quad \cdot \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi e^{-i(x-y+n-m)\phi} \left. \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
842 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\perp &= \frac{k_\perp^* N}{2} \sum_{x,y,n,m} \int dv_\perp dv_\parallel f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel) \\
843 \quad &\quad \cdot \left[iC \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{n B(k_\perp, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
844 \quad &\quad \cdot \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi e^{i(x-y+n-m)\phi} \\
845 \quad &\quad - \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \frac{n B(k_\perp, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \\
846 \quad &\quad \cdot \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi e^{-i(x-y+n-m)\phi} \left. \right]
\end{aligned}$$

847 For each of the angular integrals, we have

$$848 \quad \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi e^{\pm i(x-y+n-m)\phi} = 2\pi$$

849 only if

$$850 \quad x - y + n - m = 0$$

851 And the integral is 0 otherwise. We can then drop the y sum by substituting $y = x + n -$
 852 m :

$$853 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^{\parallel} = 2\pi k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} N \sum_{x,n,m} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$$

$$854 \quad \cdot \left[iC \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\} \right]$$

$$855 \quad - \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\}$$

$$856 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^{\perp} = \pi k_{\perp}^* N \sum_{x,n,m} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$$

$$857 \quad \cdot \left[iC \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \frac{n B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\} \right]$$

$$858 \quad - \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \frac{n B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\}$$

859 Notice that the m index is only present in the Bessel functions. We can then isolate that
 860 summation as

$$861 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^{\parallel} = 2\pi k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} N \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$$

$$862 \quad \cdot \left[iC \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\} \right]$$

$$863 \quad - \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\}$$

$$864 \quad \cdot \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)$$

$$865 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^{\perp} = \pi k_{\perp}^* N \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$$

$$866 \quad \cdot \left[iC \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \frac{n}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\} \right]$$

$$867 \quad - \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \frac{n}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\} \{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\}$$

$$868 \quad \cdot \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m)$$

869 Let us work on the m summations individually. First the easy one, where we use
 870 the Bessel function addition theorem:

$$871 \quad J_x(u \pm v) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} J_{x \mp m}(u) J_m(v)$$

872 This means we have

$$873 \quad \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_\perp\rho_e) = J_{x+n}\left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp)\rho_e\right)$$

874 The other summation is

$$875 \quad \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)B(k_\perp, \underline{n}, m)$$

$$876 \quad = \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)[J_m(k_\perp\rho_e)(J_{n-1}(k_\perp\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_\perp\rho_e))$$

$$877 \quad + J_n(k_\perp\rho_e)(J_{m-1}(k_\perp\rho_e) - J_{m+1}(k_\perp\rho_e))]$$

878 Break up into several summations,

$$879 \quad \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)B(k_\perp, \underline{n}, m)$$

$$880 \quad = (J_{n-1}(k_\perp\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_\perp\rho_e)) \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_\perp\rho_e)$$

$$881 \quad + J_n(k_\perp\rho_e) \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_{m-1}(k_\perp\rho_e)$$

$$882 \quad - J_n(k_\perp\rho_e) \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_{m+1}(k_\perp\rho_e)$$

883 Applying the Bessel function addition theorem to each,

$$884 \quad \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)B(k_\perp, \underline{n}, m)$$

$$885 \quad = (J_{n-1}(k_\perp\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_\perp\rho_e))J_{x+n}\left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp)\rho_e\right)$$

$$886 \quad + J_n(k_\perp\rho_e)J_{x+n+1}\left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp)\rho_e\right)$$

$$887 \quad - J_n(k_\perp\rho_e)J_{x+n-1}\left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp)\rho_e\right)$$

$$888 \quad \sum_m J_{x+n-m}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)B(k_\perp, \underline{n}, m)$$

$$889 \quad = J_{x+n}\left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp)\rho_e\right)[J_{n-1}(k_\perp\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_\perp\rho_e)]$$

$$890 \quad + J_n(k_\perp\rho_e)\left[J_{x+n+1}\left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp)\rho_e\right) - J_{x+n-1}\left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp)\rho_e\right)\right]$$

891 Putting these back in allows us to drop the m summation:

$$892 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\parallel = 2\pi k_\parallel^* k_\parallel N \sum_{x,n} \int dv_\perp dv_\parallel v_\perp f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel) J_{x+n}\left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp)\rho_e\right)$$

$$893 \quad \cdot \left[iC \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_n(k_\perp\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\} \right.$$

$$894 \quad \left. - \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \frac{J_n(k_\perp\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
895 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\perp &= \pi k_\perp^* N \sum_{x,n} \int dv_\perp dv_\parallel f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel) \\
896 \quad &\cdot \left[iC \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{n}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
897 \quad &- \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \frac{n}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \left. \right] \\
898 \quad &\cdot J_{x+n}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) [J_{n-1}(k_\perp \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_\perp \rho_e)] \\
899 \quad &+ J_n(k_\perp \rho_e) [J_{x+n+1}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) - J_{x+n-1}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e)]
\end{aligned}$$

900 Let us now isolate the integrals:

$$\begin{aligned}
901 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\parallel &= 2\pi k_\parallel^* k_\parallel N \sum_{x,n} \int dv_\perp v_\perp J_{x+n}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_\perp \rho_e) \\
902 \quad &\cdot \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_\parallel \left[iC \left\{ \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{1}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\} \right. \\
903 \quad &- \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \frac{1}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\} \left. \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
904 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\perp &= \pi k_\perp^* N \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_\perp J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) (J_{x+n}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) [J_{n-1}(k_\perp \rho_e) \\
905 \quad &- J_{n+1}(k_\perp \rho_e)] \\
906 \quad &+ J_n(k_\perp \rho_e) [J_{x+n+1}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) - J_{x+n-1}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e)]) \\
907 \quad &\cdot \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_\parallel \left[iC \left\{ \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{1}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
908 \quad &- \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_\parallel - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \frac{1}{\{\omega - k_\parallel v_\parallel - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \left. \right]
\end{aligned}$$

909 Define the resonances as

$$\begin{aligned}
910 \quad y_x^{hf} &= \frac{\omega_{hf} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}} \\
911 \quad y_n^{lf} &= \frac{\omega - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e}{k_\parallel}
\end{aligned}$$

912 And rearrange:

$$\begin{aligned}
913 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\parallel &= \frac{2\pi k_\parallel^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_\parallel} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_\perp v_\perp J_{x+n}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_\perp \rho_e) \\
914 \quad &\cdot \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_\parallel \left[-iC \left\{ \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{v_\parallel - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_\parallel - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right\} + \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{v_\parallel - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_\parallel - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
915 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\perp &= \frac{\pi k_\perp^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_\parallel} \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_\perp J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left(J_{x+n}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) [J_{n-1}(k_\perp \rho_e) \right. \\
916 &\quad \left. - J_{n+1}(k_\perp \rho_e)] \right. \\
917 &\quad \left. + J_n(k_\perp \rho_e) \left[J_{x+n+1}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) - J_{x+n-1}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) \right] \right) \\
918 &\quad \cdot \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_\parallel \left[iC \left\{ \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{v_\parallel - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_\parallel - y_n^{lf}\}} \right\} - \bar{C}i \left\{ \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{v_\parallel - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_\parallel - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

919 Since we are integrating $v_\parallel$ along the real axis, we can simplify the complex
920 conjugates:

$$\begin{aligned}
921 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\parallel &= \frac{4\pi k_\parallel^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_\parallel} \text{Re} \left[i\bar{C} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_\perp v_\perp J_{x+n}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_\perp \rho_e) \right. \\
922 &\quad \left. \cdot \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_\parallel \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{v_\parallel - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_\parallel - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
923 \quad \langle T \rangle_d^\perp &= \frac{2\pi k_\perp^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_\parallel} \text{Re} \left[iC \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_\perp J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left(J_{x+n}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) \right. \right. \\
924 &\quad \left. \cdot [J_{n-1}(k_\perp \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_\perp \rho_e)] \right. \\
925 &\quad \left. + J_n(k_\perp \rho_e) \left[J_{x+n+1}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) - J_{x+n-1}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) \right] \right) \\
926 &\quad \cdot \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_\parallel \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{v_\parallel - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_\parallel - y_n^{lf}\}} \left. \right]
\end{aligned}$$

927 This Bessel function term is annoying. Define

$$\begin{aligned}
928 \quad B^D(k_{hf,\perp}, k_\perp, x, n) & \\
929 &= J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left\{ J_{x+n}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) \cdot [J_{n-1}(k_\perp \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_\perp \rho_e)] \right. \\
930 &\quad \left. + J_n(k_\perp \rho_e) \left[J_{x+n+1}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) - J_{x+n-1}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

931 We can now multiply by $2v_e/N$ to get the term in the scattering power:

$$\begin{aligned}
932 \quad \langle T' \rangle_d^\parallel &= \frac{8\pi k_\parallel^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_\parallel} \text{Re} \left[i\bar{C} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_\perp v_\perp J_{x+n}((k_{hf,\perp} + k_\perp) \rho_e) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_\perp \rho_e) \right. \\
933 &\quad \left. \cdot \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_\parallel \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{v_\parallel - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_\parallel - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$934 \quad \langle T' \rangle_d^\perp = \frac{4\pi k_\perp^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_\parallel} \text{Re} \left[iC \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_\perp B^D(k_{hf,\perp}, k_\perp, x, n) \cdot \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_\parallel \frac{f_0(v_\perp, v_\parallel)}{\{v_\parallel - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_\parallel - y_n^{lf}\}} \right]$$

935 Decomposing the distribution into thermal and photoelectron terms, and using a thermal
 936 Maxwellian,

$$937 \quad f_{0m} = \frac{1}{(\pi v_{th}^2)^{3/2}} \exp \left[-\frac{(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

938 Putting this into the thermal terms and putting C back in,

$$\begin{aligned}
 939 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{d,\parallel}^{th} &= \frac{8k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\left(iZ^{hf} - \frac{i}{v_e} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) \right. \\
 940 \quad &\cdot \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_{x+n} \left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_{\perp}) \rho_e \right) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \\
 941 \quad &\cdot \left. \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right] \\
 942 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{d,\perp}^{th} &= \frac{4k_{\perp}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\left(i\overline{Z}^{hf} - \frac{i}{v_e} \overline{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \overline{U}_e^{hf} \right) \right. \\
 943 \quad &\cdot \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} B^D(k_{hf,\perp}, k_{\perp}, x, n) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \\
 944 \quad &\cdot \left. \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

945

946 The photoelectron terms are then

$$\begin{aligned}
 947 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{d,\parallel}^{ph} &= \frac{8\pi k_{\parallel}^* v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\parallel} n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\left(iZ^{hf} - \frac{i}{v_e} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) \right. \\
 948 \quad &\cdot \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_{x+n} \left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_{\perp}) \rho_e \right) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \\
 949 \quad &\cdot \left. \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right] \\
 950 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{d,\perp}^{ph} &= \frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\parallel} n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\left(i\overline{Z}^{hf} - \frac{i}{v_e} \overline{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \overline{U}_e^{hf} \right) \right. \\
 951 \quad &\cdot \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} B^D(k_{hf,\perp}, k_{\perp}, x, n) \cdot \left. \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

952 6.4 Tc Term:

953 The next term is

954
$$\langle T \rangle_c = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \mathcal{H}_j \bar{\mathcal{H}}_j'$$

955 Where we note that Y_{H1}^{hf} does not depend on velocity, and the functions $\mathcal{H}$ are

956
$$\mathcal{H}_j = i \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}}$$

957 Putting this in

958
$$\langle T \rangle_c = N |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left(i \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right)$$

959
$$\cdot \left(-i \sum_{x',y'} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{-i(x'-y')\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right)$$

960 Combining the summations and putting the integral into cylindrical coordinates,

961
$$\langle T \rangle_c = N |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \sum_{x,y,x',y'} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$$

962
$$\cdot \left(\frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right)$$

963
$$\cdot \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi e^{i(x-x'-y+y')\phi}$$

964 The integral over ϕ is again 2π if

965
$$x - x' - y + y' = 0$$

966 And 0 otherwise. We can then evaluate this integral to 2π and lose the y and lose the y
967 summation if we substitute

968
$$y = y' + x - x'$$

969
$$\langle T \rangle_c = 2\pi N |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \sum_{x,x',y'} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} \int dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$$

970
$$\cdot \left(\frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'+x-x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right)$$

971 We can isolate the y' summation as it only includes two Bessel functions:

972 $\langle T \rangle_c = 2\pi N |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \sum_{x,x'} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} \int dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$
973 $\cdot \left(\frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right)$
974 $\cdot \sum_{y'} J_{y'+x-x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)$

975 The Bessel function addition theorem is

976
$$J_x(u \pm v) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} J_{x \mp m}(u) J_m(v)$$

977 Applying this to the y' sum,

978
$$\sum_{y'} J_{y'+x-x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) = J_{x-x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e - k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) = J_{x-x'}(0)$$

979 In this case the arguments of the Bessel functions are the same, so the result is $J_{x-x'}(0)$.
980 This allows use to further simplify the summations, as we know $J_0(0) = 1$, and $J_n(0) =$
981 0 for all $n \neq 0$. Therefore we have the condition $x - x' = 0$, which lets us substitute $x =$
982 x' and drop the x' summation:

983 $\langle T \rangle_c = 2\pi N |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} \int dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$
984 $\cdot \left(\frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right)$

985 Defining the resonance as before, we can rearrange the denominators to obtain

986
$$\langle T \rangle_c = \frac{2\pi N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}}$$

987 We can now multiply by $2v_e/N$ to get the term in the scattering power:

988
$$\langle T' \rangle_c = \frac{4\pi v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}}$$

989 Separating into thermal and photoelectron terms again,

990
$$\langle T' \rangle_c^{th} = \frac{4v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right]$$

991
$$\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}} \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right]$$

992
$$\langle T' \rangle_c^{ph} = \frac{4\pi v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}}$$

993 6.5 Tb Term:

994 Moving on to the next term:

$$995 \quad \langle T \rangle_b = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[\overline{\mathcal{H}}_j' J_j \overline{Y}_{H1}^{hf} + \mathcal{H}_j \overline{J}_j' Y_{H1}^{hf} \right]$$

996 Where we have defined the following functions:

$$997 \quad \mathcal{H}_j = i \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}}$$

$$998 \quad \mathcal{J}_j = i \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}$$

$$999 \quad \cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right.$$

$$1000 \quad \left. + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}$$

1001 Putting these in, we note that the x,y sums in each function will be different, so we use

$$1002 \quad \mathcal{H}_j = i \sum_{x',y'} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x'-y')\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}}$$

1003 Then

$$1004 \quad \langle T \rangle_b$$

$$1005 \quad = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left[-i \overline{Y}_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x',y'} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{-i(x'-y')\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right.$$

$$1006 \quad \cdot i \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right.$$

$$1007 \quad \left. + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} + i Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x',y'} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x'-y')\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}}$$

$$1008 \quad \cdot (-i) \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{-i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\}$$

$$1009 \quad \cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e) e^{-i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) e^{-i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \Bigg]$$

1010 Simplify a lot and put the integration into cylindrical coordinates,

$$\begin{aligned}
1011 \quad \langle T \rangle_b &= N \sum_{x,x',y',n,m} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1012 &\cdot \left[\overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1013 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
1014 &\cdot \int d\phi e^{i(x-x'-y+y'+n-m)\phi} \\
1015 &+ \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \\
1016 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
1017 &\cdot \left. \int d\phi e^{-i(x-x'-y+y'+n-m)\phi} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1018 As before, the angular integral is only nonzero if the indexes are

$$1019 \quad x - x' - y + y' + n - m = 0$$

1020 Substituting this as $y = x - x' + y' + n - m = y' + S$ where S shorthands the rest of the
1021 indices. Isolating the terms left dependent on y :

$$\begin{aligned}
1022 \quad \langle T \rangle_b &= 2\pi N \sum_{x,x',n,m} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1023 &\cdot \left[\overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1024 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
1025 &\cdot \sum_{y'} J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'+S}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) \\
1026 &+ \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \\
1027 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
1028 &\cdot \left. \sum_{y'} J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'+S}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1029 With the Bessel function addition theorem we have $\sum_{y'} J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'+S}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) = 1$
1030 if $S = 0$, and the summation equal to 0 if $S \neq 0$. Therefore we can collapse the y'
1031 summation and gain the condition $S = x - x' + n - m = 0$. Substituting $m = x - x' +$
1032 n , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
1033 \quad \langle T \rangle_b &= 2\pi N \sum_{x,x',n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1034 &\cdot \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1035 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{x-x'+n}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, x - x' + n)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
1036 &+ Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \\
1037 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{x-x'+n}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, x - x' + n)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1038 There is nothing more we can do on the summations from a strictly exact point of
1039 view. In the appendix it is justified that when we have terms like

$$1040 \quad \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}}$$

1041 The residues of the diagonal terms $x = x'$ are of the order $\frac{1}{v_e}$, and the residues of the off-
1042 diagonal terms are of the order $\frac{1}{[(x-x')\omega_{ce}]} \sim \frac{1}{\omega_{ce}}$ since obviously $x - x' \neq 0$. With typical
1043 ionospheric parameters, $\omega_{ce} \gg v_e$, and therefore $\frac{1}{v_e} \gg \frac{1}{\omega_{ce}}$ and the diagonal terms are
1044 typically larger. Also, it's a lot easier to move forward dropping the off-diagonal terms.
1045 Making the approximation $x = x'$, we then have

$$\begin{aligned}
1046 \quad \langle T \rangle_b &= 2\pi N \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1047 &\cdot \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{1}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1048 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n^2(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
1049 &+ Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{1}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \\
1050 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n^2(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1051 The two terms dependent on n suggest breaking this into two terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
1052 \quad \langle T \rangle_{b,\parallel} &= 2\pi k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} N \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1053 \quad &\cdot \left[\frac{\overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{1}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1054 \quad &\cdot \left. \left\{ \frac{1}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\} + Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1055 \quad &\cdot \left. \frac{1}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \cdot \left. \left\{ \frac{1}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1056 \quad \langle T \rangle_{b,\perp} &= \pi k_{\perp}^* N \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n) f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1057 \quad &\cdot \left[\frac{\overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \cdot \frac{1}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1058 \quad &\cdot \left. \left\{ \frac{1}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\} + Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1059 \quad &\cdot \left. \frac{1}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \cdot \left. \left\{ \frac{1}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1060 Rearranging the denominators and substituting the defined resonances:

$$\begin{aligned}
1061 \quad \langle T \rangle_{b,\parallel} &= \frac{2\pi k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1062 \quad &\cdot \left[\frac{\overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}}}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right. \\
1063 \quad &\left. + Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1064 \quad \langle T \rangle_{b,\perp} &= -\frac{\pi k_{\perp}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}} \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n) f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1065 \quad &\cdot \left[\frac{\overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}}}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \right. \\
1066 \quad &\left. + Y_{H1}^{hf} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1067 At this point we choose to do the integration numerically, and therefore $v_{\parallel}$ is only
1068 real valued. This let's us simplify both equations as the terms in [] are complex
1069 conjugates:

$$\begin{aligned}
1070 \quad \langle T \rangle_{b,\parallel} &= \frac{4\pi k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
1071 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1072 \quad \langle T \rangle_{b,\perp} &= -\frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n) \right. \\
1073 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1074 We can now multiply by $2v_e/N$ to get the term in the scattering power:

$$\begin{aligned}
1075 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{b,\parallel} &= \frac{8\pi k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
1076 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1077 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{b,\perp} &= -\frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n) \right. \\
1078 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1079 Decomposing the distribution into thermal and photoelectron terms using

$$1080 \quad f_{0m} = \frac{1}{(\pi v_{th}^2)^{3/2}} \exp \left[-\frac{(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

1081 We have

1082

1083

$$\begin{aligned}
1084 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{b,\parallel}^{th} &= \frac{8k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right. \\
1085 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right] \\
1086 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{b,\perp}^{th} &= -\frac{4k_{\perp}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right. \\
1087 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1088 And the photoelectron terms are

$$\begin{aligned}
1089 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{b,\parallel}^{ph} &= \frac{8\pi k_{\parallel}^* v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel} n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
1090 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right] \\
1091 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{b,\perp}^{ph} &= -\frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel} n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n) \right. \\
1092 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

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1103 6.6 Ta Term:

1104 The last term to work out is

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$$\langle T \rangle_a = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) J_j \bar{J}_j'$$

1106 Where we have defined

1107
$$J_j = i \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}$$

1108
$$\cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right.$$

1109
$$\left. + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}$$

1110 Since we're multiplying the J 's we put ' marks on the indices of one set. Then

1111
$$\langle T \rangle_a = N \int d\vec{v}^3 f_0(\vec{v}) \left(i \left\{ \sum_{x,y} \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(x-y)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right.$$

1112
$$\cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right.$$

1113
$$\left. + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}$$

1114
$$\cdot \left(-i \left\{ \sum_{x',y'} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) e^{-i(x'-y')\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right.$$

1115
$$\cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n',m'} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) e^{-i(n'-m')\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right.$$

1116
$$\left. + \frac{n'k_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \sum_{n',m'} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m') e^{-i(n'-m')\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\}$$

1117 Put into cylindrical coordinates and simplify a lot.

$$\begin{aligned}
1118 \quad \langle T \rangle_a &= N \sum_{\substack{x,y,n,m \\ x',y',n',m'}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \left(\frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1119 &\quad \cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right) \\
1120 &\quad \cdot \left(\frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right) \\
1121 &\quad \cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} + \frac{n'k_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right) \\
1122 &\quad \cdot \int d\phi e^{i(x-y)\phi} e^{i(n-m)\phi} e^{-i(x'-y')\phi} e^{-i(n'-m')\phi}
\end{aligned}$$

1123 Simplify some more,

$$\begin{aligned}
1124 \quad \langle T \rangle_a &= N \sum_{\substack{x,y,n,m \\ x',y',n',m'}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1125 &\quad \cdot \left(\frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_y(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right. \\
1126 &\quad \cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right) \\
1127 &\quad \cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} + \frac{n'k_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right) \\
1128 &\quad \cdot \int d\phi e^{i(x-y-x'+y'+n-m-n'+m')\phi}
\end{aligned}$$

1129 We now play with the indices. As before, the angular integral is only nonzero if

$$1130 \quad x - y - x' + y' + n - m - n' + m' = 0$$

1131 Choosing to write this as

$$1132 \quad y = y' + x - x' + n - m - n' + m' \equiv y' + S$$

1133 We then have

$$\begin{aligned}
1134 \quad \langle T \rangle_a &= 2\pi N \sum_{\substack{x,n,m \\ x',n',m'}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1135 &\cdot \left(\frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right. \\
1136 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
1137 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} + \frac{n'k_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right) \\
1138 &\cdot \sum_{y'} J_{y'+S}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{y'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)
\end{aligned}$$

1139 As before, the summation over Bessel functions is 1 if $S = 0$ and 0 otherwise. Then we
1140 have

$$1141 \quad x - x' + n - m - n' + m' = 0$$

1142 Which we can use as $m = m' + x - x' + n - n' = m' + S$:

$$\begin{aligned}
1143 \quad \langle T \rangle_a &= 2\pi N \sum_{\substack{x,n \\ x',n',m'}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1144 &\cdot \left(\frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right. \\
1145 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \right. \\
1146 &\cdot \left. \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} + \frac{n'k_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

1147 To evaluate this any further we need to multiply out the n, m terms. We then have

$$\begin{aligned}
1148 \quad \langle T \rangle_a &= 2\pi N \sum_{\substack{x,n \\ x',n',m'}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \\
1149 &\cdot \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - x'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \\
1150 &\cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right. \\
1151 &+ \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \\
1152 &+ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \frac{n'k_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \\
1153 &+ \left. \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{n'k_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1154 Simplify some. And for compactness substitute the y_x^{hf} resonances:

$$\begin{aligned}
1155 \quad \langle T \rangle_a &= \frac{2\pi N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,\underline{n}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\}} \\
1156 &\quad \cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^{*2} k_{\parallel}^2 \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right. \\
1157 &\quad + \frac{nk_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel}}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \\
1158 &\quad + \frac{n'k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel}}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \\
1159 &\quad \left. + \frac{nn'k_{\perp}^{*2}}{4v_{\perp}^2} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1160 This suggests breaking into 3 different terms:

$$1161 \quad \langle T \rangle_a = \langle T \rangle_{a,1} + \langle T \rangle_{a,2} + \langle T \rangle_{a,3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1162 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,1} &= \frac{2\pi N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,\underline{n}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\}} \\
1163 &\quad \cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^{*2} k_{\parallel}^2 \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1164 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2} &= \frac{2\pi N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,\underline{n}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\}} \\
1165 &\quad \cdot \left\{ \frac{nk_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel}}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}^2} \right. \\
1166 &\quad \left. + \frac{n'k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel}}{2v_{\perp}} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1167 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,3} &= \frac{2\pi N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,\underline{n}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\}} \\
1168 &\quad \cdot \left\{ \frac{nn'k_{\perp}^{*2}}{4v_{\perp}^2} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S)}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \frac{B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n'\omega_{ce} + iv_e\}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1169 Simplify some and put the resonances into the denominators:

$$\begin{aligned}
1170 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,1} &= \frac{2\pi k_{\parallel}^{*2} N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,\underline{n}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\}} \\
1171 &\quad \cdot \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}^2} \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1172 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2} &= -\frac{\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\}} \\
1173 \quad &\cdot \left\{ \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}^2} \sum_{m'} J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) \right. \\
1174 \quad &\left. + \frac{n' J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m') \right\} \\
1175 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,3} &= \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} N}{2k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} nn' \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{v_{\perp}} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\}} \\
1176 \quad &\cdot \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} \sum_{m'} B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')
\end{aligned}$$

1177 From here we will work out each term separately as the Bessel function products become
1178 messy.

1179 6.7 Ta1

1180 First the easy one,

$$\begin{aligned}
1181 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,1} &= \frac{2\pi k_{\parallel}^{*2} N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\}} \\
1182 \quad &\cdot \frac{J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}^2} \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)
\end{aligned}$$

1183 In this case the summation is 1 if $S = 0$, and 0 otherwise. Then we have $x - x' + n -$
1184 $n' = 0$, which we substitute as

$$1185 \quad n' = n + x - x'$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1186 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,1} &= \frac{2\pi k_{\parallel}^{*2} N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,x',n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\}} \\
1187 \quad &\cdot \frac{J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{J_{n+x-x'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+x-x'}^{lf}}\}^2}
\end{aligned}$$

1188 As before, we cannot manipulate the indices any further. Using the diagonal
1189 approximation we take $x = x'$ (note we could have also substituted for x' and then
1190 approximated $n = n'$. If one set of indices is diagonalized then the other necessarily is).
1191 Then

1192 $\langle T \rangle_{a,1} = \frac{2\pi k_{\parallel}^{*2} N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,x',n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} v_{\perp} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}}$

1193 $\cdot \frac{J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2}$

1194 Separate the integrals,

1195 $\langle T \rangle_{a,1} = \frac{2\pi k_{\parallel}^{*2} N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,x',n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e)$

1196 $\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2}$

1197 We can now multiply by $2v_e/N$ to get the term in the scattering power:

1198 $\langle T' \rangle_{a,1} = \frac{4\pi k_{\parallel}^{*2} v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,x',n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e)$

1199 $\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2}$

1200 Decomposing the distribution into thermal and photoelectron terms using

1201 $f_{0m} = \frac{1}{(\pi v_{th}^2)^{3/2}} \exp \left[-\frac{(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1202 We then have

1203 $\langle T' \rangle_{a,1}^{th} = \frac{4k_{\parallel}^{*2} v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1204 $\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1205 $\langle T' \rangle_{a,1}^{ph} = \frac{4\pi k_{\parallel}^{*2} v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e)$

1206 $\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2}$

1207

1208 6.8 Ta2:

1209 Next is

$$\begin{aligned}
1210 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2} &= -\frac{\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{\substack{x,n \\ x',n'}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_{x'}^{hf}\}} \\
1211 \quad &\cdot \left\{ \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_{n'}^{lf}\}^2} \sum_{m'} J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) \right. \\
1212 \quad &\left. + \frac{n' J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_{n'}^{lf}\}} \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m') \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1213 Where we have

$$\begin{aligned}
1214 \quad B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) &= J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \\
1215 \quad &\quad + J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{m-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))
\end{aligned}$$

1216 The two m' sums are similar but need to be worked out separately. One at a time,

$$\begin{aligned}
1217 \quad \sum_{m'} J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) \\
1218 \quad &= \sum_{m'} J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \\
1219 \quad &\quad + J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{m'+S-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{m'+S+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \\
1220 \quad \sum_{m'} J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m' + S) \\
1221 \quad &= (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \sum_{m'} J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \\
1222 \quad &\quad + J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \sum_{m'} J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{m'+S-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \\
1223 \quad &\quad - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \sum_{m'} J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{m'+S+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)
\end{aligned}$$

1224 With $S = x - x' + n - n'$ we apply the Bessel function addition theorem:

$$\begin{aligned}
1225 \quad \sum_{m'} J_{m'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) \\
1226 \quad &= (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \delta\{S\} + J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \delta\{S - 1\} \\
1227 \quad &\quad - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \delta\{S + 1\}
\end{aligned}$$

1228 The delta function will be kept so we can put the correct index conditions back into the
1229 full equation. Doing the same for the other sum,

$$\begin{aligned}
1230 \quad & \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m') \\
1231 \quad & = \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) [J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) (J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \\
1232 \quad & + J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) (J_{m'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{m'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))] \\
1233 \quad & \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m') \\
1234 \quad & = (J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \\
1235 \quad & + J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \\
1236 \quad & - J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{m'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \\
1237 \quad & \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m') \\
1238 \quad & = (J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \delta\{S\} + J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \delta\{S+1\} \\
1239 \quad & - J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \delta\{S-1\}
\end{aligned}$$

1240 Putting these back in,

$$\begin{aligned}
1241 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2} & = -\frac{\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{\substack{x,n \\ x',n'}} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_{x'}^{hf}\}} \\
1242 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_{n'}^{lf}\}^2} [(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \delta\{S\} \right. \\
1243 \quad & + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \delta\{S-1\} - J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \delta\{S+1\}] \\
1244 \quad & + \frac{n' J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - y_{n'}^{lf}\}} [(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \delta\{S\} \\
1245 \quad & \left. + J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \delta\{S+1\} - J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \delta\{S-1\}] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1246 Focusing only on the n and n' terms we collect by argument of delta function:

$$\begin{aligned}
1247 \quad T_n &= \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}^2} \delta\{S\} \right. \\
1248 &\quad + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}^2} \delta\{S - 1\} \\
1249 &\quad \left. - J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}^2} \delta\{S + 1\} \right] \\
1250 &\quad + \left[(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \frac{n'J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} \delta\{S\} \right. \\
1251 &\quad + J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{n'J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} \delta\{S + 1\} \\
1252 &\quad \left. - J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{n'J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} \delta\{S - 1\} \right] \\
1253 \quad T_n &= \delta\{S\} \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}^2} \right. \\
1254 &\quad \left. + (J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \frac{n'J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} \right] \\
1255 &\quad + \delta\{S - 1\} \left[J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}^2} \right. \\
1256 &\quad \left. - J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{n'J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} \right] \\
1257 &\quad + \delta\{S + 1\} \left[J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{n'J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} \right. \\
1258 &\quad \left. - J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1259 Putting in the index condition as $n' + S = x - x' + n$, or knowing we're going to take
1260 $x = x'$ in the next step, $n' = n - S$:

$$\begin{aligned}
1261 \quad T_n &= \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right. \\
1262 \quad &\quad \left. + (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \frac{nJ_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right] \\
1263 \quad &+ \left[J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\}^2} \right. \\
1264 \quad &\quad \left. - J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{(n-1)J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\}} \right] \\
1265 \quad &+ \left[J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{(n+1)J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} \right. \\
1266 \quad &\quad \left. - J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1267 Can do some simplification:

$$\begin{aligned}
1268 \quad T_n &= n J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \left[\frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right. \\
1269 \quad &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right] \\
1270 \quad &\quad + J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[\frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\}^2} \right. \\
1271 \quad &\quad \left. - \frac{(n-1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\}} \right] \\
1272 \quad &\quad + J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[\frac{(n+1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} \right. \\
1273 \quad &\quad \left. - \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1274 Putting this back in, along with $x = x'$,

$$\begin{aligned}
1275 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2} &= -\frac{\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{n,f,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x^2(k_{n,f,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\}} \\
1276 \quad &\cdot \left\{ n J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \left[\frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\}^2} \right. \right. \\
1277 \quad &\left. \left. + \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right] \right. \\
1278 \quad &\left. + J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[\frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\}^2} \right. \right. \\
1279 \quad &\left. \left. - \frac{(n-1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\}} \right] \right. \\
1280 \quad &\left. + J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[\frac{(n+1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}}^{lf}\}} \right. \right. \\
1281 \quad &\left. \left. - \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}}^{lf}\}^2} \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1282 We can simplify the last two terms by doing the n sums separately:

$$\begin{aligned}
1283 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2} &= -\frac{\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\}} \\
1284 \quad &\cdot \left\{ \sum_n n J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \left[\frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\}^2} \right. \right. \\
1285 \quad &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right] \right. \\
1286 \quad &\quad \left. + \sum_n J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[\frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\}^2} \right. \right. \\
1287 \quad &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{(n-1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\}} \right] \right. \\
1288 \quad &\quad \left. + \sum_n J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[\frac{(n+1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}}^{lf}\}} \right. \right. \\
1289 \quad &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}}^{lf}\}^2} \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1290 In the last summation we can change the index to $m = n + 1$, and as the summation is
1291 still infinite, this gives

$$\begin{aligned}
1292 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2} &= -\frac{\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\}} \\
1293 \quad &\cdot \left\{ \sum_n n J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \left[\frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\}^2} \right. \right. \\
1294 \quad &\left. \left. + \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right] \right. \\
1295 \quad &\left. + \sum_n J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[\frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\}^2} \right. \right. \\
1296 \quad &\left. \left. - \frac{(n-1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\}} \right] \right. \\
1297 \quad &\left. + \sum_m J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{m-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[\frac{m}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_{m-1}^{lf}\}^2 \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_m}^{lf}\}} \right. \right. \\
1298 \quad &\left. \left. - \frac{(m-1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_{m-1}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_m}^{lf}\}^2} \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1299 The last two summations are similar other than $m \rightarrow n$, and therefore can be combined:

$$\begin{aligned}
1300 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2} &= -\frac{\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\}} \\
1301 \quad &\cdot \left\{ n J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \left[\frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\}^2} \right. \right. \\
1302 \quad &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right] \right. \\
1303 \quad &\quad \left. + J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[\frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\}^2} \right. \right. \\
1304 \quad &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_{n-1}^{lf}\}^2} - \frac{(n-1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right. \right. \\
1305 \quad &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{(n-1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_{n-1}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\}^2} \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1306 Since we are integrating over the real line, we can assume $v_{\parallel}$ is real, which means we
1307 have complex conjugates every where:

$$\begin{aligned}
1308 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2} &= -\frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\}} \right. \\
1309 \quad &\cdot \left. \left\{ \frac{n J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n}^{lf}\}^2} + \frac{n J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\}^2} \right. \right. \\
1310 \quad &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{(n-1) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1311 The $v_{\perp}$ integration is cleaner if we separate based on Bessel functions, and the $v_{\parallel}$
1312 integrating code works best if there are no additive terms, so we break this up as

$$1313 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2} = \langle T \rangle_{a,2.1} + \langle T \rangle_{a,2.2} + \langle T \rangle_{a,2.3}$$

1314 Where we have

$$\begin{aligned}
1315 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2.1} &= -\frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \right. \\
1316 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1317 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2.2} &= -\frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
1318 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1319 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2.3} &= \frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} (n-1) \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
1320 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1321 We can now multiply by $2v_e/N$ to get the term in the scattering power:

$$\begin{aligned}
1322 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2.1} &= -\frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
1323 \quad &\quad \left. - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1324 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2.2} &= -\frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
1325 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1326 $\langle T \rangle_{a,2.3} = \frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} (n-1) \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$

1327 $\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right]$

1328 Decomposing the distribution into thermal and photoelectron terms using

1329
$$f_{0m} = \frac{1}{(\pi v_{th}^2)^{3/2}} \exp \left[-\frac{(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

1330 The thermal terms are

1331 $\langle T \rangle_{a,2.1} = -\frac{4k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$

1332 $\left. - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right) \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1333 $\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]$

1334 $\langle T \rangle_{a,2.2} = -\frac{4k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right.$

1335 $\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]$

1336 $\langle T \rangle_{a,2.3} = \frac{4k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} (n \right.$

1337 $\left. - 1) \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right.$

1338 $\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]$

1339

1340 And the photoelectrons are

1341

$$\langle T \rangle_{a,2.1} = -\frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$$

1342

$$\left. - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right] \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2}$$

1343

$$\langle T \rangle_{a,2.2} = -\frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$$

1344

$$\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\}^2} \right]$$

1345

$$\langle T \rangle_{a,2.3} = \frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} (n-1) \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$$

1346

$$\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \right]$$

1347

1348

1349

1350

6.9 Ta3:

1351

The last term is

1352

$$\langle T \rangle_{a,3} = \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^2 N}{2k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x',n'} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{v_{\perp}} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{x'}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}^{hf}}\}}$$

1353

$$\cdot \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \sum_{m'} \frac{n'}{m'} B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')$$

1354

Where the Bessel function product is

1355

$$B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m) = J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))$$

1356

$$+ J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{m-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))$$

1357

Have to expand the product in the m' summation:

1358

$$\sum_{m'} B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')$$

1359

$$= \sum_{m'} \{J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))$$

1360

$$+ J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{m'+S-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{m'+S+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))\}$$

1361

$$\cdot \{J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))$$

1362

$$+ J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{m'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{m'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))\}$$

1363

$$\sum_{m'} B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')$$

1364

$$= \sum_{m'} \{J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)$$

1365

$$- J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))$$

1366

$$+ J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{m'+S-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{m'+S+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)$$

1367

$$- J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))$$

1368

$$+ J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{m'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)$$

1369

$$- J_{m'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))$$

1370

$$+ J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{m'+S-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{m'+S+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{m'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)$$

1371

$$- J_{m'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))\}$$

1372

$$\sum_{m'} B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m')$$

1373

$$= (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))$$

1374

$$\cdot \sum_{m'} J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))$$

1375

$$\cdot \sum_{m'} (J_{m'+S-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{m'+S+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))$$

1376

$$+ (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)$$

1377

$$\cdot \sum_{m'} (J_{m'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{m'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'+S}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))$$

1378

$$+ J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)$$

1379

$$\cdot \sum_{m'} (J_{m'+S-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{m'+S+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)$$

1380

$$- J_{m'+S-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) + J_{m'+S+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{m'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))$$

1381

Go through doing the Bessel function addition theorem:

$$\begin{aligned}
1382 \quad & \sum_{m'} B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m') \\
1383 \quad & = (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \cdot \delta(S) \\
1384 \quad & + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \cdot (\delta(S-1) - \delta(S+1)) \\
1385 \quad & + (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \cdot (\delta(S+1) - \delta(S-1)) \\
1386 \quad & + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \cdot (2\delta(S) - \delta(S+2) - \delta(S-2))
\end{aligned}$$

1387 Group together by index condition:

$$\begin{aligned}
1388 \quad & \sum_{m'} B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, m' + S) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}', m') \\
1389 \quad & = [(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \\
1390 \quad & + 2J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)] \cdot \delta(S) \\
1391 \quad & + \delta(S+1)[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \\
1392 \quad & - J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))] \\
1393 \quad & + \delta(S-1)[J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \\
1394 \quad & - (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)] - J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \\
1395 \quad & \cdot \delta(S+2) - J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_{n'}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) \cdot \delta(S-2)
\end{aligned}$$

1396 Where we evaluate $S = x - x' + n - n'$ as $n' = n - S + x - x'$, and then make the
1397 diagonal approximation of $x = x'$ to obtain the index condition of $n' = n - S$, leaving
1398 only the x and n summations. Putting this all in,

1399

$$\begin{aligned}
1400 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,3} &= \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} N}{2k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{v_{\perp}} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}} \\
1401 \quad &\cdot \left\{ [(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))(J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \right. \\
1402 \quad &+ 2J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)] \cdot \delta(S) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{n'}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} \\
1403 \quad &+ \delta(S+1) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{n'}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} [(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \\
1404 \quad &- J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))] \\
1405 \quad &+ \delta(S-1) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{n'}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} [J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n'-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n'+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \\
1406 \quad &- (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)] - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \\
1407 \quad &\cdot \delta(S+2) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{n'}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n'}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \\
1408 \quad &\cdot \delta(S-2) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{n'}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n'}^{lf}}\}} \left. \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1409 Substitute for n' :

$$\begin{aligned}
1410 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,3} &= \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} N}{2k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{v_{\perp}} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}} \\
1411 \quad &\cdot \left\{ [(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))^2 + 2J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e)] \frac{n^2}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right. \\
1412 \quad &+ \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{(n+1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} [(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \\
1413 \quad &- J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))] \\
1414 \quad &+ \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{(n-1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\}} [J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \\
1415 \quad &- (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)] \\
1416 \quad &- J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{(n+2)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+2}^{lf}}\}} \\
1417 \quad &- J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}} \frac{(n-2)}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-2}^{lf}}\}} \left. \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1418 Since the n summation is infinite, for the $\delta(S - 1)$ and $\delta(S - 2)$ terms we can relabel the
 1419 summation index to essentially shift the sum up by 1 or 2, respectively. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 1420 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,3} &= \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} N}{2k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{v_{\perp}} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}} \\
 1421 &\quad \cdot \left\{ \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))^2 + 2J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right] \frac{n^2}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right. \\
 1422 &\quad + \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
 1423 &\quad \left. - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \right] \\
 1424 &\quad + \frac{(n+1)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_{n+1}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \left[J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \right. \\
 1425 &\quad \left. - (J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right] \\
 1426 &\quad - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+2}^{lf}}\}} \\
 1427 &\quad \left. - J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \frac{(n+2)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_{n+2}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

1428 We will integrate $v_{\parallel}$ numerically along the real line, so we can identify complex
 1429 conjugates and simplify:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1430 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,3} &= \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} N}{2k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{v_{\perp}} f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) \frac{J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}} \\
 1431 &\quad \cdot \left\{ \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))^2 + 2J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right] \frac{n^2}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right. \\
 1432 &\quad + 2\text{Re} \left[\frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \right. \\
 1433 &\quad \left. \left. - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \right] \right. \\
 1434 &\quad \left. - 2J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \text{Re} \left[\frac{n}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+2}^{lf}}\}} \right] \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

1435 The differing sets of poles once again suggest splitting into 3 terms:

$$1436 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,3} = \langle T \rangle_{a,3.1} + \langle T \rangle_{a,3.2} + \langle T \rangle_{a,3.3}$$

1437

$$\begin{aligned}
1438 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,3.1} &= \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} N}{2k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n^2 \int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))^2 \right. \\
1439 \quad &\quad \left. + 2J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right] \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1440 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,3.2} &= \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n(n+1) \\
1441 \quad &\cdot \operatorname{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \right. \\
1442 \quad &\quad \left. \left. - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \right] \right. \\
1443 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1444 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,3.3} &= -\frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} N}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n(n+2) \\
1445 \quad &\cdot \operatorname{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
1446 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+2}^{lf}}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1447 We can now multiply by $2v_e/N$ to get the term in the scattering power:

$$\begin{aligned}
1448 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.1} &= \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n^2 \int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))^2 \right. \\
1449 \quad &\quad \left. + 2J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right] \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1450 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.2} &= \frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n(n+1) \\
1451 \quad &\cdot \operatorname{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \right. \\
1452 \quad &\quad \left. \left. - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \right] \right. \\
1453 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1454 $\langle T' \rangle_{a,3.3} = -\frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n(n+2)$

1455 $\cdot \operatorname{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$

1456 $\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+2}^{lf}}\}} \right]$

1457 Decomposing the distribution into thermal and photoelectron terms using

1458 $f_{0m} = \frac{1}{(\pi v_{th}^2)^{3/2}} \exp \left[-\frac{(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1459 We have the thermal terms

1460 $\langle T' \rangle_{a,3.1} = \frac{k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n^2 \int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) [(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))^2$

1461 $+ 2J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e)] \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1462 $\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1463 $\langle T' \rangle_{a,3.2} = \frac{2k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n(n+1)$

1464 $\cdot \operatorname{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) [(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$

1465 $\left. - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))] \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]$

1466 $\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1467 $\langle T' \rangle_{a,3.3} = -\frac{2k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n(n+2)$

1468 $\cdot \operatorname{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]$

1469 $\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+2}^{lf}}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1470

1471 And the photoelectron terms

$$1472 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.1}^{ph} = \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2 n_{0m}} \sum_{x,n} n^2 \int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))^2 \right. \\ 1473 \quad \left. + 2J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right] \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}}$$

$$1474 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.2}^{ph} = \frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2 n_{0m}} \sum_{x,n} n(n+1) \\ 1475 \quad \cdot \operatorname{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) [(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\ 1476 \quad \left. - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))] \right. \\ 1477 \quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} \right]$$

$$1478 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.3}^{ph} = -\frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2 n_{0m}} \sum_{x,n} n(n+2) \\ 1479 \quad \cdot \operatorname{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\ 1480 \quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+2}^{lf}}\}} \right]$$

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1491 **7. Results**

1492 For completeness, the results are compiled together here.

1493 **Definitions**

1494 Delta frequency and wavenumber:

1495
$$\omega^* = \omega - \omega_{hf}$$

1496
$$\vec{k}^* = \vec{k} - \vec{k}_{hf}$$

1497 The Landau/cyclotron velocities follow a simple notation:

1498
$$y_a^* = \frac{[\omega^* - a\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}$$

1499
$$y_x^{hf} = \frac{\omega_{hf} - x\Omega_{ce} - iv_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}}$$

1500
$$y_n^{lf} = \frac{\omega - n\Omega_{ce} - iv_e}{k_{\parallel}}$$

1501 The electron distribution is broken up into a thermal Maxwellian and photoelectron
1502 terms:

1503
$$f_{0e} = f_{0m} + \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} f_{0h}$$

1504
$$f_{0m} = \frac{1}{(\pi v_{th}^2)^{3/2}} \exp\left[-\frac{(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)}{v_{th}^2}\right]$$

1505

1506 **Summary**

1507 The discretized scattering power is

1508 The nonlinear term in the perturbed density is then

1509
$$\left\langle |n_{1e}[\omega, \vec{k}]|^2 \right\rangle_{NL} = S_{NL} = \left| \frac{1 + \chi_i}{\epsilon} \right|^2 \frac{1}{|1 - U_e|^2} \frac{\epsilon_0^2 \gamma^2 \Delta \kappa^2 \omega_{pe}^4 k_{hf}^4}{4\pi^6 e^2 n_0^2 k^{*2}} |E_1[\omega^*, \vec{k}^*]|^2 \cdot \langle T \rangle$$

1510 Note how trivial it is to calculate the summation over κ_i from this – take multiple k_{hf}
1511 choices and add the results of n_{1e} .

1512

1513

1514 **<T> Terms**

1515 Need to evaluate <T>, which was broken into many different terms. We have

1516
$$\langle T \rangle = \langle T \rangle_a + \langle T \rangle_b + \langle T \rangle_c + \langle T \rangle_d + \langle T \rangle_e + \langle T \rangle_f$$

1517 Each of these terms gets broken up into smaller pieces, each with a thermal (th) and
1518 photoelectron (ph) sub-term:

$$1519 \quad \langle T \rangle_a = \langle T \rangle_{a,1} + \langle T \rangle_{a,2,1} + \langle T \rangle_{a,2,2} + \langle T \rangle_{a,2,3} + \langle T \rangle_{a,3,1} + \langle T \rangle_{a,3,2} + \langle T \rangle_{a,3,3}$$

$$1520 \quad \langle T \rangle_b = \langle T \rangle_{b,\parallel} + \langle T \rangle_{b,\perp}$$

$$1521 \quad \langle T \rangle_c = \langle T \rangle_c$$

$$1522 \quad \langle T \rangle_d = \langle T \rangle_{d,\parallel} + \langle T \rangle_{d,\perp}$$

$$1523 \quad \langle T \rangle_e = \langle T \rangle_e$$

$$1524 \quad \langle T \rangle_f = \langle T \rangle_f$$

1525 Ta Term

1526 A1 Term

$$1527 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,1}^{th} = \frac{4k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

$$1528 \quad \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

$$1529 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,1}^{ph} = \frac{4\pi k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e)$$

$$1530 \quad \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2}$$

1531

1532 A2 Term

1533 The thermal terms are

$$1534 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2,1}^{th} = -\frac{4k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$$

$$1535 \quad \left. - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right) \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

$$1536 \quad \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \Bigg]$$

$$1537 \quad \langle T \rangle_{a,2,2}^{th} = -\frac{4k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right.$$

$$1538 \quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]$$

1539 $\langle T \rangle_{a,2.3}^{th} = \frac{4k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} (n \right.$

1540 $\quad - 1) \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1541 $\quad \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_{n-1}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \left. \right]$

1542

1543 And the photoelectrons are

1544 $\langle T \rangle_{a,2.1}^{ph} = -\frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$

1545 $\quad \left. - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right) \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \left. \right]$

1546 $\langle T \rangle_{a,2.2}^{ph} = -\frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$

1547 $\quad \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n-1}^{lf}}\}^2} \left. \right]$

1548 $\langle T \rangle_{a,2.3}^{ph} = \frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{x,n} (n-1) \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$

1549 $\quad \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{x'}}^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_{n-1}^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}^2} \left. \right]$

1550

1551

1552 A3 Term

1553 The thermal terms are

$$\begin{aligned}
1554 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.1}^{th} &= \frac{k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n^2 \int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))^2 \right. \\
1555 \quad &\quad \left. + 2J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right] \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \\
1556 \quad &\quad \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \\
1557 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.2}^{th} &= \frac{2k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n(n+1) \\
1558 \quad &\quad \cdot \operatorname{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \right. \\
1559 \quad &\quad \left. \left. - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) \right] \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right. \\
1560 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right] \\
1561 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.3}^{th} &= -\frac{2k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2} \sum_{x,n} n(n+2) \\
1562 \quad &\quad \cdot \operatorname{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right. \\
1563 \quad &\quad \left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+2}^{lf}}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1564

1565 And the photoelectron terms

$$\begin{aligned}
1566 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.1}^{ph} &= \frac{\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2 n_{0m}} \sum_{x,n} n^2 \int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left[(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))^2 \right. \\
1567 \quad &\quad \left. + 2J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right] \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1568 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.2}^{ph} &= \frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2 n_{0m}} \sum_{x,n} n(n+1) \\
1569 \quad &\cdot \text{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) [(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
1570 \quad &\left. - J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))] \right. \\
1571 \quad &\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+1}^{lf}}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1572 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{a,3.3}^{ph} &= -\frac{2\pi k_{\perp}^{*2} v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}^2 n_{0m}} \sum_{x,n} n(n+2) \\
1573 \quad &\cdot \text{Re} \left[\int \frac{dv_{\perp}}{v_{\perp}} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+2}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right. \\
1574 \quad &\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_{n+2}^{lf}}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1575

1576 **Tb Term**

1577 We have

$$1578 \quad \langle T \rangle_b = \langle T \rangle_{b,\parallel} + \langle T \rangle_{b,\perp}$$

1579 Where

$$1580 \quad B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n) = 2J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) (J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1581 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{b,\parallel}^{th} &= \frac{8k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}} \text{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right. \\
1582 \quad &\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1583 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{b,\perp}^{th} &= -\frac{4k_{\perp}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel}} \text{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right. \\
1584 \quad &\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1585 And the photoelectron terms are

1586
$$\langle T' \rangle_{b,\parallel}^{ph} = \frac{8\pi k_{\parallel}^* v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel} n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n^2(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \right.$$

1587
$$\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right]$$

1588
$$\langle T' \rangle_{b,\perp}^{ph} = -\frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 k_{\parallel} n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_{H1}^{hf} \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) B(k_{\perp}, \underline{n}, n) \right.$$

1589
$$\left. \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right]$$

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Tc Term

1595
$$\langle T' \rangle_c^{th} = \frac{4v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}^2} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

1596
$$\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

1597
$$\langle T' \rangle_c^{ph} = \frac{4\pi v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel}^2 n_{0m}} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\}}$$

1598

1599

Td Term

1600

For the $\langle E \rangle_d$ term we initially obtained

1601

$$\langle T \rangle_d = \langle T \rangle_d^{\parallel} + \langle T \rangle_d^{\perp}$$

1602

The perpendicular derivative terms use the product of Bessel functions:

1603

$$B^D(k_{hf,\perp}, k_{\perp}, x, n)$$

1604

$$= J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \left\{ J_{x+n} \left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_{\perp}) \rho_e \right) \cdot [J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)] \right.$$

1605

$$\left. + J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[J_{x+n+1} \left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_{\perp}) \rho_e \right) - J_{x+n-1} \left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_{\perp}) \rho_e \right) \right] \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1606 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{d,\parallel}^{th} &= \frac{8k_{\parallel}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\left(iZ^{hf} - \frac{i}{v_e} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) \right. \\
1607 \quad &\cdot \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_{x+n} \left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_{\perp}) \rho_e \right) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \\
1608 \quad &\cdot \left. \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1609 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{d,\perp}^{th} &= \frac{4k_{\perp}^* v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\left(i\overline{Z^{hf}} - \frac{i}{v_e} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \overline{U_e^{hf}} \right) \right. \\
1610 \quad &\cdot \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} B^D(k_{hf,\perp}, k_{\perp}, x, n) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \\
1611 \quad &\cdot \left. \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

1612

1613 The photoelectron terms are then

$$\begin{aligned}
1614 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{d,\parallel}^{ph} &= \frac{8\pi k_{\parallel}^* v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\parallel} n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\left(iZ^{hf} - \frac{i}{v_e} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) \right. \\
1615 \quad &\cdot \sum_{x,n} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_{x+n} \left((k_{hf,\perp} + k_{\perp}) \rho_e \right) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \\
1616 \quad &\cdot \left. \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1617 \quad \langle T' \rangle_{d,\perp}^{ph} &= \frac{4\pi k_{\perp}^* v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\parallel} n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\left(i\overline{Z^{hf}} - \frac{i}{v_e} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \overline{U_e^{hf}} \right) \right. \\
1618 \quad &\cdot \sum_{x,n} n \int dv_{\perp} B^D(k_{hf,\perp}, k_{\perp}, x, n) \cdot \left. \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_x^{hf}}\} \{v_{\parallel} - \overline{y_n^{lf}}\}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

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Te Term

$$\langle T' \rangle_e^{th} = \frac{8v_e}{v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi} k_{hf,\parallel}} \operatorname{Re} \left[i \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right. \\ \left. \cdot \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] \right]$$

1626

$$\langle T' \rangle_e^{ph} = \frac{8\pi v_e n_{0h}}{k_{hf,\parallel} n_{0m}} \operatorname{Re} \left[i \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} - \frac{1}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 U_e^{hf} \right) \right.$$

1627

$$\left. \cdot \sum_x \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x^2(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \right]$$

1628

1629

1630

Tf Term

$$\langle T' \rangle_f = 2 \left(Z^{hf} \overline{Y_{H1}^{hf}} \overline{U_e^{hf}} + \overline{Z^{hf}} Y_{H1}^{hf} U_e^{hf} \right) + 2v_e |Z^{hf}|^2 + \frac{2}{v_e} |Y_{H1}^{hf}|^2 |U_e^{hf}|^2$$

1631

1632

1633

Z and Y Terms

1634

1635 The special functions used in $\langle T \rangle$.

1636 Which are broken up as

$$Y^{hf} = Y_1^{hf} + Y_2^{hf} + Y_3^{hf} + Y_4^{hf}$$

1637

$$Z^{hf} = Z_1^{hf} + Z_2^{hf} + Z_3^{hf} + Z_4^{hf}$$

1638

1639

1640 We break Z_1^{hf} into thermal and photoelectron terms based on the linearity of f_{0e} , with1641 $Z_1^{hf} = Z_1^{th} + Z_1^{ph}$, and so forth with each other Z term. (Code uses Z_1^p instead of Z_1^{ph})1642 The Z^{hf} and Y^{hf} terms require the following two integrals:

$$I^1(v_{\perp}) = \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

1643

$$I^2(v_{\perp}) = \int dv_{\perp} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right] J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x-1}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \right.$$

1644

$$\left. - J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x+1}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \right]$$

1645

$$+ \left(J_{x-1}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) - J_{x+1}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) \right) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

1646

1647 The first integral is used in $Z_1^{th}, Z_2^{th}, Z_3^{th}, Y_1^{th}, Y_2^{th}, Y_3^{th}$. The second integral is used in
 1648 Z_4^{th}, Y_4^{th} . There may be similar overlap in the photoelectron $v_{\perp}$ integrals.

1649 **NOTE:** In the photoelectron expressions we need $f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$ and its derivatives
 1650 evaluated with the Landau/cyclotron resonance $y_n^{lf} = (\omega - n\Omega_{ce})/k_{\parallel}$. This is a problem
 1651 computationally since we therefore have f_{0h} as a function of $v_{\perp}$ and the low-frequency
 1652 variable ω . To reduce computation time, we note that $\omega \ll \Omega_{ce}$, and *only for evaluating*
 1653 $f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$ we will make the approximation $y_n^{lf} \approx (-n\Omega_{ce})/k_{\parallel}$. This will reduce
 1654 computation time significantly, and we keep the proper ω dependence everywhere else.

1655 The Z terms are then

$$1656 \quad Z_1^{th} = -\frac{4ik_{\parallel}^*}{k_{hf,\parallel}k_{\parallel}v_{th}^5\sqrt{\pi}} \sum_{n,x} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp}$$

$$1657 \quad + k_{hf,\perp}]) \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right] \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{v_{\parallel}}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \left(\exp\left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right]\right)$$

$$1658 \quad Z_1^{ph} = \frac{2\pi ik_{\parallel}^*}{k_{hf,\parallel}k_{\parallel}} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \sum_{n,x} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

$$1659 \quad \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \frac{\partial f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel}}$$

1660

$$1661 \quad Z_2^{th} = -\frac{4i\Omega_{ce}}{k_{\parallel}k_{hf,\parallel}v_{th}^5\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \sum_{n,x} n \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp}$$

$$1662 \quad + k_{hf,\perp}]) \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right] \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right]$$

$$1663 \quad Z_2^{ph} = \frac{2\pi i\Omega_{ce}}{k_{\parallel}k_{hf,\parallel}} \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \sum_{n,x} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

$$1664 \quad \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \frac{\partial f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\perp}}$$

1665

$$1666 \quad Z_3^{th} = \frac{2ik_{\parallel}^*}{k_{\parallel}k_{hf,\parallel}v_{th}^3\sqrt{\pi}} \sum_{n,x} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e) J_x(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right]$$

$$1667 \quad \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\}\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}^2} \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right]$$

1668
$$Z_3^{ph} = \frac{2\pi i k_{\parallel}^* n_{0h}}{k_{\parallel} k_{hf,\parallel} n_{0m}} \sum_{n,x} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

1669
$$\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}^2}$$

1670

1671
$$Z_4^{th} = \frac{i}{k_{\parallel} v_{th}^3 \sqrt{\pi}} \frac{k_{hf,\perp} k_{\perp}^*}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\perp}} \sum_{n,x} n \int dv_{\perp} \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right] J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x-1}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} \right.$$

1672
$$+ k_{hf,\perp}])$$

1673
$$- J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x+1}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

1674
$$+ (J_{x-1}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) - J_{x+1}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \left. \right]$$

1675
$$\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right]$$

1676
$$Z_4^{ph} = \frac{i\pi k_{hf,\perp} k_{\perp}^* n_{0h}}{k_{\parallel} k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\perp} n_{0m}} \sum_{n,x} n \int dv_{\perp} J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x-1}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \right.$$

1677
$$- J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x+1}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

1678
$$+ (J_{x-1}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) - J_{x+1}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \left. \right]$$

1679
$$\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_{0h}}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}}$$

1680

1681 **Yhf Term**

1682 The Y^{hf} function is broken into 4 parts, with $Y^{hf} = Y_1^{hf} + Y_2^{hf} + Y_3^{hf} + Y_4^{hf}$.

1683 Note the dependence on Z^{hf} let's us also write

1684
$$Y^{hf} = v_e Z^{hf} + Y_{Y1}^{hf} + Y_{Y2}^{hf} + Y_{Y3}^{hf} + Y_{Y4}^{hf}$$

1685 Where the Y_Y^{hf} terms are further broken into thermal and photoelectron terms as for

1686 example

1687
$$Y_{Y1}^{hf} = Y_{Y1}^{th} + Y_{Y1}^{ph}$$

1688 And we defined

1689
$$Y_{H1}^{hf} = \frac{Y^{hf}}{1 + H_1^{hf}}$$

1690 These terms are

1691
$$Y_{Y1}^{th} = \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{k_{hf}^2} \frac{4k_{\parallel}^*}{v_{th}^5 \sqrt{\pi} k_{\parallel} k_{hf,\parallel}} \sum_{n,x} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp}$$

1692
$$+ k_{hf,\perp}]) \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right]$$

1693
$$\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right] \left[k_{hf,\parallel} \left(2 \frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} - 1\right)$$

1694
$$+ 2x\Omega_{ce} \frac{v_{\parallel}}{v_{th}^2} \right]$$

1695
$$Y_{Y1}^{ph} = \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{k_{hf}^2} \frac{2\pi k_{\parallel}^*}{k_{hf,\parallel} k_{\parallel}} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \sum_{n,x} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

1696
$$\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \left[k_{hf,\parallel} \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel}^2} + \frac{x\Omega_{ce}}{v_{\perp}} \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel} \partial v_{\perp}} \right]$$

1697

1698
$$Y_{Y2}^{th} = \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{k_{hf}^2} \frac{8\Omega_{ce}}{v_{th}^7 \sqrt{\pi} k_{\parallel} k_{hf,\parallel}} \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \sum_{n,x} n \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

1699
$$\cdot \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right] \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{[k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} + x\Omega_{ce}]}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right]$$

1700
$$Y_{Y2}^{ph} = \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{k_{hf}^2} \frac{2\pi\Omega_{ce}}{k_{\parallel} k_{hf,\parallel}} \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \sum_{n,x} n \int dv_{\perp} J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

1701
$$\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \left[k_{hf,\parallel} \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel} \partial v_{\perp}} + \frac{x\Omega_{ce}}{v_{\perp}} \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\perp}^2} \right]$$

1702

1703
$$Y_{Y3}^{th} = -\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{k_{hf}^2} \frac{4k_{\parallel}^*}{v_{th}^5 \sqrt{\pi} k_{\parallel} k_{hf,\parallel}} \sum_{n,x} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

1704
$$\cdot \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right] \cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{[k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} + x\Omega_{ce}]}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}^2} \exp\left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2}\right]$$

1705
$$Y_{Y3}^{ph} = \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{k_{hf}^2} \frac{2\pi k_{\parallel}^*}{k_{\parallel} k_{hf,\parallel}} \frac{n_{0h}}{n_{0m}} \sum_{n,x} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}])$$

1706
$$\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}^2} \left[k_{hf,\parallel} \frac{\partial f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{x\Omega_{ce}}{v_{\perp}} \frac{\partial f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right]$$

1707

1708 $Y_{Y^4}^{th} = -\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{k_{hf}^2} \frac{2}{v_{th}^5 \sqrt{\pi} k_{\parallel}} \frac{k_{hf,\perp}}{k_{hf,\parallel}} \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \sum_{n,x} n \int dv_{\perp} J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x-1}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} \right.$

1709 $\left. + k_{hf,\perp}]) \right.$

1710 $\left. - J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x+1}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \right.$

1711 $\left. + (J_{x-1}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) - J_{x+1}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \right] \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\perp}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1712 $\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{[k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} + x \Omega_{ce}]}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \exp \left[-\frac{v_{\parallel}^2}{v_{th}^2} \right]$

1713 $Y_{Y^4}^{ph} = \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{k_{hf}^2} \frac{\pi}{k_{\parallel}} \frac{k_{hf,\perp}}{k_{hf,\parallel}} \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \frac{n_{oh}}{n_{om}} \sum_{n,x} n \int dv_{\perp} J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) \left[J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x-1}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \right.$

1714 $\left. - J_x(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_{n+x+1}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \right.$

1715 $\left. + (J_{x-1}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) - J_{x+1}(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e)) J_{n+x}(\rho_e [k_{\perp} + k_{hf,\perp}]) \right]$

1716 $\cdot \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{1}{\{v_{\parallel} - y_n^{lf}\} \{v_{\parallel} - y_x^{hf}\}} \left[k_{hf,\parallel} \frac{\partial f_{oh}}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{x \Omega_{ce}}{v_{\perp}} \frac{\partial f_{oh}}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right]$

1717

1718

1719 **Appendices**

1720 The following sections are appendices for the derivation.

1721 **Appendix A: Ensemble averages**

1722 In this appendix the ensemble average of density fluctuations in an unmagnetized
 1723 plasma will be worked out to show how this process will be applied to the nonlinear
 1724 terms in derivation.

1725 The ensemble averaging is defined as

$$1726 \quad \langle X \rangle = \frac{\int dv X(v) P(v)}{\int dv P(v)} \quad (3.1)$$

1727 Where $P(v)$ is the probability of finding the system in state v , and there can be
 1728 multiple v coordinates (ie $\int dv_1 dv_2 \dots dv_N$). Checking this with the math in section 3.4
 1729 of *Froula et al. (2011)*, we look to evaluate

$$1730 \quad \left\langle \sum_j \frac{e^{i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)}}{\omega - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma} \cdot \sum_m \frac{e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r}_m(0)}}{\omega - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma} \right\rangle$$

$$1731 \quad = \left\langle \sum_m \sum_j \frac{e^{i\vec{k} \cdot (\vec{r}_j(0) - \vec{r}_m(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)} \right\rangle$$

1732 (3.2)

1733 The weighting factor used for the initial velocities is the equilibrium distribution,
 1734 $f_0(\vec{v})$. By using f_0 and not F_0 , the normalization is simple: $\int dv P(v) = \int dv f_0(v) = 1$.

1735 The ensemble average is then

$$1736 \quad \left\langle \sum_m \sum_j \frac{e^{i\vec{k} \cdot (\vec{r}_j(0) - \vec{r}_m(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)} \right\rangle$$

$$1737 \quad = \int_{v_1} dv_1 f_0(v_1) \int_{v_2} dv_2 f_0(v_2) \int_{v_3} dv_3 \dots \int_{v_N} dv_N$$

$$1738 \quad \cdot \left[\sum_m \sum_j \frac{f_0(v_N) e^{i\vec{k} \cdot (\vec{r}_j(0) - \vec{r}_m(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)} \right]$$

1739 (3.3)

1740 We can enumerate the double summation:

$$\begin{aligned}
1741 & \left\langle \sum_m \sum_j \frac{e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_j(0)-r_m(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)} \right\rangle \\
1742 & = \int_{v_1} dv_1 f_0(v_1) \int_{v_2} dv_2 f_0(v_2) \dots \int_{v_N} dv_N \left[\frac{f_0(v_N) e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_1(0)-r_1(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_1(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_1(0) + i\gamma)} \right] \\
1743 & + \int_{v_1} dv_1 f_0(v_1) \int_{v_2} dv_2 f_0(v_2) \dots \int_{v_N} dv_N \left[\frac{f_0(v_N) e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_1(0)-r_2(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_1(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_2(0) + i\gamma)} \right] \\
1744 & + \dots \\
1745 & + \int_{v_1} dv_1 f_0(v_1) \int_{v_2} dv_2 f_0(v_2) \dots \int_{v_N} dv_N \left[\frac{f_0(v_N) e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_1(0)-r_N(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)} \right] \\
1746 & + \dots \\
1747 & + \int_{v_1} dv_1 f_0(v_1) \int_{v_2} dv_2 f_0(v_2) \dots \int_{v_N} dv_N \left[\frac{f_0(v_N) e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_2(0)-r_1(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_2(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_1(0) + i\gamma)} \right] \\
1748 & + \int_{v_1} dv_1 f_0(v_1) \int_{v_2} dv_2 f_0(v_2) \dots \int_{v_N} dv_N \left[\frac{f_0(v_N) e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_2(0)-r_2(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_2(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_2(0) + i\gamma)} \right] \\
1749 & + \dots \\
1750 & + \int_{v_1} dv_1 f_0(v_1) \int_{v_2} dv_2 f_0(v_2) \dots \int_{v_N} dv_N \left[\frac{f_0(v_N) e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_N(0)-r_N(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_N(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_N(0) + i\gamma)} \right] \\
1751 & \tag{3.4}
\end{aligned}$$

1752 Now the integrals dv_j over terms without the same variable v_j present will simply
1753 evaluate to 1, so

$$\begin{aligned}
1754 & \left\langle \sum_m \sum_j \frac{e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_j(0)-r_m(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)} \right\rangle \\
1755 & = \int_{v_1} dv_1 \left[\frac{f_0(v_1)}{([\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_1(0)]^2 + \gamma^2)} \right] \\
1756 & + \int_{v_1} dv_1 \int_{v_2} dv_2 \left[\frac{f_0(v_1)f_0(v_2) e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_1(0)-r_2(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_1(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_2(0) + i\gamma)} \right] + \dots \\
1757 & + \int_{v_1} dv_1 \int_{v_N} dv_N \left[\frac{f_0(v_1)f_0(v_N) e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_1(0)-r_N(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)} \right] + \dots \\
1758 & + \int_{v_1} dv_1 \int_{v_2} dv_2 \left[\frac{f_0(v_1)f_0(v_2) e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_2(0)-r_1(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_2(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_1(0) + i\gamma)} \right] \\
1759 & + \int_{v_2} dv_2 \left[\frac{f_0(v_2)}{([\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_2(0)]^2 + \gamma^2)} \right] + \dots \\
1760 & + \int_{v_N} dv_N \left[\frac{f_0(v_N)}{([\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_N(0)]^2 + \gamma^2)} \right] \\
1761 & \tag{3.5}
\end{aligned}$$

1762 It is clear that all the integrals reduced down to one variable if $j = m$, and to two
1763 variables if $j \neq m$. Since there are N^2 terms in the double summation, and N terms of that
1764 have $j = m$, then there are $N(N - 1)$ terms with $j \neq m$.

1765 Now we break the summation into two parts, one with $j = m$ (identical particles),
1766 and one with $j \neq m$.

$$\begin{aligned}
1767 & \left\langle \sum_j \frac{e^{i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}_j(0)}}{\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma} \cdot \sum_m \frac{e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}_m(0)}}{\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma} \right\rangle \\
1768 & = \left\langle \sum_m \frac{e^0}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0))^2 + \gamma^2} \right. \\
1769 & \left. + \sum_m \sum_{j \neq m} \frac{e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_j(0)-r_m(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)} \right\rangle \\
1770 & \tag{3.6}
\end{aligned}$$

1771 The ensemble averaging then takes place over all v coordinates ($dv_1 dv_2 \dots dv_N$),

1772
$$\left\langle \sum_j \frac{e^{i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}_j(0)}}{\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma} \cdot \sum_m \frac{e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}_m(0)}}{\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma} \right\rangle$$

1773
$$= \int dv_1 dv_2 \dots dv_N \frac{f_0}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0))^2 + \gamma^2}$$

1774
$$+ \left\langle \sum_m \sum_{j \neq m} \frac{e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_j(0)-r_m(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)} \right\rangle$$

1775 (3.7)

1776 Skipping some formality (namely what f_0 is a function of), the result of the nested
1777 integrals is

1778
$$\left\langle \sum_j \frac{e^{i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}_j(0)}}{\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma} \cdot \sum_m \frac{e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}_m(0)}}{\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma} \right\rangle$$

1779
$$= N \int dv \frac{f_0(v)}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0))^2 + \gamma^2}$$

1780
$$+ \left\langle \sum_m \sum_{j \neq m} \frac{e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_j(0)-r_m(0))}}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)} \right\rangle$$

1781 (3.8)

1782 The N comes from resolving the summation of nested integrals. Similar work on
1783 the double sum gives

1784
$$\left\langle \sum_j \frac{e^{i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}_j(0)}}{\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma} \cdot \sum_m \frac{e^{-i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}_m(0)}}{\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma} \right\rangle$$

1785
$$= N \int dv \frac{f_0(v)}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}(0))^2 + \gamma^2}$$

1786
$$+ N(N-1) \int \int_{j \neq m} dv_m dv_j \frac{f_0(v_m) f_0(v_j) \langle e^{i\vec{k}\cdot(\vec{r}_j(0)-r_m(0))} \rangle}{(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_j(0) - i\gamma)(\omega - \vec{k}\cdot\vec{v}_m(0) + i\gamma)}$$

1787 (3.9)

1788 In the integrals, the (0) time dependence can be dropped since the weighting
1789 factor is present. In the double integral term the average $\langle \rangle$ is 0 for particles that are either
1790 initially uncorrelated, or in positions close to equilibrium.

1791
1792

1793 **Appendix B: Bessel Function identity**

1794 We need to evaluate summations of a product of Bessel functions. The Bessel
1795 function addition theorem is

$$1796 \quad J_s(u \pm v) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} J_{s \mp m}(u) J_m(v) \quad (3.9)$$

1797 For the top signs this is

$$1798 \quad J_s(u + v) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} J_{s-m}(u) J_m(v) \quad (3.10)$$

1799 Which is directly used in several places of the full derivation.

1800 For the bottom signs, when $u = v$, we have

$$1801 \quad J_s(0) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} J_{m+s}(u) J_m(u) \quad (3.11)$$

1802 Now $J_0(0) = 1$, and $J_s(0) = 0$ for all $s \neq 0$. Therefore we have the needed
1803 identity for Bessel functions:

$$1804 \quad \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} J_{m+s}(u) J_m(u) = 0 \quad \text{for } s \neq 0 \quad (3.12)$$

$$1805 \quad \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} J_{m+s}(u) J_m(u) = 1 \quad \text{for } s = 0 \quad (3.13)$$

1806

1807

1808 **Appendix C: Klimontovich Formalism**

1809 The derivation uses the Klimontovich formalism from *Froula et al. (2011)*, where
1810 the distribution is defined as a product of delta functions at each particle location in phase
1811 space:

$$1812 \quad F_{1s}[t, \vec{r}, \vec{v}] = F_s[t, \vec{r}, \vec{v}] - F_{0s}[\vec{v}] = \sum_j^{N_s} \delta[\vec{r} - \vec{r}_j(t)] \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] - F_{0s}[\vec{v}] \quad (3.14)$$

$$1813 \quad n_{1s}[t, \vec{r}] = n_s - n_{0s} = \sum_v d\vec{v} F_s[t, \vec{r}, \vec{v}] - n_{0s} = \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{r} - \vec{r}_j(t)] - n_{0s} \quad (3.15)$$

1814 We need to evaluate the initial state term in G_e .

$$\begin{aligned}
1815 \quad & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* n}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1816 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] \right. \\
1817 \quad & \left. - in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}]f_{0e}] \right\} \\
1818 \quad & = \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* n}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1819 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1820 \quad & - \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* n}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1821 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}]f_{0e}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1822 \quad & = \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* n}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1823 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1824 \quad & - \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^* n}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1825 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}]f_{0e}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1826 The perturbed density is simply

$$1827 \quad n_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}] = \int d\vec{v} f_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] = \sum_j^N \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0))$$

1828 The Klimontovich formalism really just substitutes $\int d\vec{v} \rightarrow \sum_v d\vec{v}$ as a discretization of
1829 the velocity, and $F_{1s}[t, \vec{r}, \vec{v}] = \sum_j^{N_s} \delta[\vec{r} - \vec{r}_j(t)]\delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)]$ for the formal definition of
1830 the particle distribution. The delta functions remove the integral over velocity, leaving the
1831 summation over particles, and the exponential factor comes from the spatial Fourier
1832 transform since we only want $F_{1s}[t, \vec{k}, \vec{v}]$. This gives

1833

$$f_1[t, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] = \int d\vec{r} \exp(i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r}) f_1[t, \vec{r}, \vec{v}]$$

1834

$$= \sum_j^N \int d\vec{r} \exp(i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r}) \delta[\vec{r} - \vec{r}_j(t)] \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)]$$

1835

$$f_1[t, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] = \int d\vec{r} \exp(i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r}) f_1[t, \vec{r}, \vec{v}] = \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r}_j(t))$$

1836

$$n_1[t, \vec{k}] = \int d\vec{v} f_1[t, \vec{k}, \vec{v}] = \int d\vec{v} \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r}_j(t)) = \sum_j^N \exp(i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r}_j(t))$$

1837

Using this in the first term of what we want, noting the argument of f_1 and n_1 is $\vec{k}_{hf}$,

1838

$$\int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_e) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} n \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right)$$

1839

$$\cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) e^{i(l-p)\phi} i f_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \right\}$$

1840

$$= \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e) J_m(k_{\perp} \rho_e) e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp} \rho_e} n \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right)$$

1841

$$\cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) J_p(k_{hf,\perp} \rho_e) e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel} v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - i\nu_e\}} \right\} \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf}$$

1842

$$\cdot \vec{r}_j(t))$$

1843

In this form, we need to expand the derivatives out before collapsing the velocity integral

1844

with the delta function. However, chain ruling the derivatives will eventually lead to

1845

$\frac{\partial}{\partial v} \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)]$. Taking the derivative of the delta function is a mess and prone to error.

1846

Instead, we will do integration by parts. To do this, we first note $d\vec{v} = \vec{v}_{\perp} dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} d\phi$.

1847

Doing each derivative separately,

$$\begin{aligned}
1848 \quad & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right) \\
1849 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] \right\} = \\
1850 \quad & = \int_{\vec{v}} v_{\perp} dv_{\perp} d\phi \int dv_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right) \\
1851 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \\
1852 \quad & \cdot \vec{r}_j(t)) \\
1856 \quad & = \int_{\vec{v}} v_{\perp} dv_{\perp} d\phi \left[\sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} (k_{\parallel}^*) \right. \\
1857 \quad & \cdot \left. \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} \right. \\
1858 \quad & \left. - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(t)) \right] \Bigg|_{-\infty}^{\infty} \\
1859 \quad & - \int_{\vec{v}} v_{\perp} dv_{\perp} d\phi \int dv_{\parallel} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1860 \quad & \cdot \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \\
1861 \quad & \cdot \vec{r}_j(t)) \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1853 In the boundary term, no particles exist at $\vec{v}_j = \pm\infty$, so the argument of the delta function
1854 will never be zero, and therefore $\delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] = 0$ and the boundary term can be
1855 dropped. We then obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
1862 \quad & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right) \\
1863 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1864 \quad & = - \int_{\vec{v}} v_{\perp} dv_{\perp} d\phi \int dv_{\parallel} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1865 \quad & \cdot \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \\
1866 \quad & \cdot \vec{r}_j(t)) \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1867 \quad & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right) \\
1868 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1869 \quad & = - \int_{\vec{v}} v_{\perp} dv_{\perp} dv_{\parallel} d\phi \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1870 \quad & \cdot \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \\
1871 \quad & \cdot \vec{r}_j(t)) \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1872 Now the delta function can kill the integral, and evaluate at $t = 0$,

$$\begin{aligned}
1873 \quad & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right) \\
1874 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1875 \quad & = - \sum_j^N \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1876 \quad & \cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\} e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)}
\end{aligned}$$

1877 Similarly for the $\partial/\partial v_{\perp}$ term,

$$\begin{aligned}
1878 \quad & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(\frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} \frac{n}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1879 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1880 \quad & = \int_{\vec{v}} dv_{\parallel} d\phi \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(\frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} \frac{n}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1881 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \\
1882 \quad & \cdot \vec{r}_j(t))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1883 \quad & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(\frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} \frac{n}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1884 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1885 \quad & = \left[v_{\perp} \sum_n \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(\frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} \frac{n}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \right. \\
1886 \quad & \cdot \left. \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} \right. \\
1887 \quad & \left. - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(t)) \right] \Bigg|_0^{\infty} \\
1888 \quad & - \int_{\vec{v}} dv_{\parallel} d\phi \int dv_{\perp} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1889 \quad & \cdot \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(t)) \\
1890 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \left(\frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \frac{n}{\rho_e} \right) v_{\perp} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1891 Now $\rho_e = v_{\perp}/\omega_{ce}$, so we have $\frac{v_{\perp}}{\rho_e} = \omega_{ce}$. The boundary term evaluates to 0 on the upper
1892 bound since again no particles will have $v_{\perp} = \infty$, and therefore $\delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)]_{\infty} = 0$. For
1893 the lower bound, it's possible to have $v_{\perp} = 0$. Looking at the rest of the term, we note
1894 that for $n, l \neq 0$, $J_{n,l}(0) = 0$. This gives an indeterminate form as $J_n^2(0)J_l^2(0)\delta(0)$, which
1895 Wolfram Alpha says evaluates to 0. For the case of both $n = 0$ and $l = 0$, the Bessel
1896 functions are nonzero, but there is a leading factor of n , so $n \delta(0) = 0$ as that is not a

1897 limit, but a removal of the $n = 0$ term from the summation. Therefore the boundary term
 1898 vanishes again, and we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(\frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \frac{n}{\rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
 & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
 & = - \int_{\vec{v}} dv_{\parallel} d\phi \int dv_{\perp} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
 & \cdot \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(t)) \\
 & \cdot \left\{ \left(\frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} n\omega_{ce} \right) \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

1904 Evaluating the derivative of the Bessel function, with $k_{\perp}\rho_e = \frac{k_{\perp}}{\omega_{ce}} v_{\perp}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(\frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} \frac{n}{\rho_e} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
 & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
 & = - \int_{\vec{v}} dv_{\parallel} d\phi \int dv_{\perp} \left\{ \sum_l \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
 & \cdot \sum_j^N \delta[\vec{v} - \vec{v}_j(t)] \exp(i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(t)) \\
 & \cdot \left\{ \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}} n\omega_{ce} \sum_n \frac{\frac{k_{\perp}}{\omega_{ce}} e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
 & \cdot [J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e)) \\
 & \left. + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)(J_{m-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_e))] \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

1912 Then killing the velocity integral with the delta function, we note that $\delta[\vec{v}]$ is a 3D
 1913 distribution with units of $1/v^3$, and therefore is in Cartesian coordinates. We then have to
 1914 transform the integral from cylindrical coordinates back to Cartesian by multiplying by
 1915 $v_{\perp}/v_{\perp}$ and obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
1916 \quad & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(\frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} \frac{n}{\partial v_{\perp}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1917 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] \right\} \\
1918 \quad & = - \sum_j^N \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1919 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp,j}(0)} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{i\vec{k}_{hf}\cdot\vec{r}_j(0)} e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1920 \quad & \cdot \left[J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \left(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \right) \right. \\
1921 \quad & \left. \left. + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \left(J_{m-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \right) \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1922 So together we have

$$\begin{aligned}
1923 \quad & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} \frac{n}{\partial v_{\perp}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1924 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] \right\} \\
1925 \quad & = - \sum_j^N \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1926 \quad & \cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right\} e^{i\vec{k}_{hf}\cdot\vec{r}_j(0)} \\
1927 \quad & - \sum_j^N \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1928 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp,j}(0)} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{i\vec{k}_{hf}\cdot\vec{r}_j(0)} e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right. \\
1929 \quad & \cdot \left[J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \left(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \right) \right. \\
1930 \quad & \left. \left. + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \left(J_{m-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \right) \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1931 \quad & \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} n \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1932 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}] \right\} \\
1933 \quad & = - \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\} \\
1934 \quad & \cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right. \\
1935 \quad & + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp,j}(0)} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \\
1936 \quad & \cdot \left[J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \left(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \right) \right. \\
1937 \quad & \left. \left. + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \left(J_{m-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \right) \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1938

1939 We then need

$$\begin{aligned}
1940 \quad & - \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} n \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1941 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}]f_{0e}] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1942 Since n_{1e} is independent of velocity, it can be pulled out of the integral and is not
1943 affected by the derivatives, so we have

$$\begin{aligned}
1944 \quad & -n_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}] \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} n \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \\
1945 \quad & \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [if_{0e}] \right\} \\
1946 \quad & = - \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf} \cdot \vec{r}_j(0)} \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \right. \\
1947 \quad & \left. + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} n \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right) \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [if_{0e}] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

1948

1949 We will then short hand the closed form integral to

$$1950 \quad Z^{hf} = \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} n \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right)$$

$$1951 \quad \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [if_{0e}] \right\}$$

1952 Then we have

$$1953 \quad -n_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}] \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} n \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right)$$

$$1954 \quad \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [if_{0e}] \right\} = - \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf}\cdot\vec{r}_j(0)} Z^{hf}$$

1955 So the end result is

$$1956 \quad \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_e)J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel} - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \left(k_{\parallel}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} + \frac{k_{\perp}^*}{k_{\perp}\rho_e} n \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \right)$$

$$1957 \quad \cdot \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_e)e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel} - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} [if_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}, \vec{v}]] \right.$$

$$1958 \quad \left. - in_{1e}[t_0, \vec{k}_{hf}]F_{0e} \right\}$$

$$1959 \quad = - \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf}\cdot\vec{r}_j(0)} \left\{ \sum_{l,p} \frac{i J_l(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))J_p(k_{hf,\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(l-p)\phi}}{\{\omega_{hf} - k_{hf,\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - l\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right\}$$

$$1960 \quad \cdot \left\{ k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel} \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0))e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}^2} \right.$$

$$1961 \quad \left. + \frac{nk_{\perp}^*}{2v_{\perp,j}(0)} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{i(n-m)\phi}}{\{\omega - k_{\parallel}v_{\parallel,j}(0) - n\omega_{ce} - iv_e\}} \right.$$

$$1962 \quad \cdot \left[J_m(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \left(J_{n-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) - J_{n+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \right) \right.$$

$$1963 \quad \left. + J_n(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \left(J_{m-1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) - J_{m+1}(k_{\perp}\rho_j(0)) \right) \right] \left\{ \right.$$

$$1964 \quad \left. - \sum_j^N e^{i\vec{k}_{hf}\cdot\vec{r}_j(0)} Z^{hf} \right.$$

1965

1966

1967 **Appendix D: Diagonalizing Double Sums**

1968 In evaluating $\langle E \rangle$, we come across many double summations nested in the velocity
1969 integrals, such as

$$1970 \quad E = \int dv_{\parallel} dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} f_0(\vec{v}) \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{\omega^* - k_{\parallel}^* v_{\parallel} - m\Omega_e - iv_e} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{\omega^* - k_{\parallel}^* v_{\parallel} - n\Omega_e + iv_e} H(v_{\parallel})$$

1971 Where $H(v_{\parallel})$ just stands in for other terms.

1972 We want to justify diagonalizing the double sum, that is taking only the
1973 $a = a'$ terms. To see why we can do this, we work out the integration as

$$1974 \quad E$$

$$1975 \quad = \sum_{n,m} \int dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) H(v_{\parallel})}{\omega^* - k_{\parallel}^* v_{\parallel} - m\Omega_e - iv_e} \frac{1}{\omega^* - k_{\parallel}^* v_{\parallel} - n\Omega_e + iv_e}$$

1976 We will work under the assumption that $H(v_{\parallel})$ has a pole at V , which is separate
1977 from the two poles already here. We then have

$$1978 \quad E$$

$$1979 \quad = \sum_{n,m} \int dv_{\perp} \frac{v_{\perp}}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) H(v_{\parallel})}{v_{\parallel} - \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}} \frac{1}{v_{\parallel} - \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}}$$

1980 The integral is then

$$1981 \quad I = \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel}) H(v_{\parallel})}{v_{\parallel} - \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}} \frac{1}{v_{\parallel} - \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}}$$

$$1982 \quad I = \pi i \text{Res} \left[\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] - \pi i \text{Res} \left[\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] + \pi i \text{Res}[V]$$

1983 Where without loss of generality we've assumed the pole V is in the upper half of
1984 the complex plane. The residues are straightforward,

$$1985 \quad \text{Res} \left[\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] = \frac{f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right)}{\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} - \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}}$$

$$1986 \quad \text{Res} \left[\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right]$$

$$1987 \quad = \frac{k_{\parallel}^*}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right)$$

1988

$$1989 \quad \text{Res} \left[\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] = \frac{f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right)}{\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} - \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}}$$

$$1990 \quad \text{Res} \left[\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right]$$

$$1991 \quad = - \frac{k_{\parallel}^*}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right)$$

$$1992 \quad \text{Res}[V] = \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, V)H'(V)}{V - \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}} \frac{1}{V - \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}}$$

1993 Then we have

$$1994 \quad I$$

$$1995 \quad = \frac{\pi i k_{\parallel}^*}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right)$$

$$1996 \quad + \pi i \frac{k_{\parallel}^*}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right)$$

$$1997 \quad + \pi i \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, V)H'(V)}{V - \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}} \frac{1}{V - \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}}$$

1998 The first two terms can factor:

$$1999 \quad I = \frac{\pi i k_{\parallel}^*}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} \left\{ f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right.$$

$$2000 \quad \left. + f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right\}$$

$$2001 \quad + \pi i \frac{f_0(v_{\perp}, V)\bar{H}(V)}{V - \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}} \frac{1}{V - \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*}}$$

2002 Where $\bar{H}$ is H with the pole removed. Let's simplify the denominator in the last
2003 term,

$$2004 \quad d = \left(V - \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \cdot \left(V - \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right)$$

$$2005 \quad = V^2 - V \left[\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} + \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right]$$

$$2006 \quad + \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e][\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^* k_{\parallel}^*}$$

$$2007 \quad d = V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - (m+n)\Omega_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] + \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e][\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + iv_e[n-m]\Omega_e + v_e^2}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}}$$

2008

So the integral is

$$\begin{aligned}
 2009 \quad I &= \frac{\pi i k_{\parallel}^*}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} \left\{ f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right. \\
 2010 &\quad \left. + f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right\} \\
 2011 &\quad + \pi i f_0(v_{\perp}, V) H'(V) \left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - (m+n)\Omega_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] \right. \\
 2012 &\quad \left. + \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e][\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + iv_e[n-m]\Omega_e + v_e^2}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} \right\}^{-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

2013

And the whole term is

$$\begin{aligned}
 2014 \quad &E \\
 2015 \quad &= \sum_{n,m} \int dv_{\perp} \frac{v_{\perp}}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) \\
 2016 &\cdot \left[\frac{\pi i k_{\parallel}^*}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} \left\{ f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right. \right. \\
 2017 &\quad \left. \left. + f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right\} \right. \\
 2018 &\quad \left. + \pi i f_0(v_{\perp}, V) \bar{H}(V) \left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - (m+n)\Omega_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] \right. \right. \\
 2019 &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e][\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + iv_e[n-m]\Omega_e + v_e^2}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} \right\}^{-1} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

2020

Let's break this up into two terms: the first term with the poles at ω^* , and the last

2021

term with the generic pole at V .

2022

$$\begin{aligned}
 2023 \quad &E^1 \\
 &= \sum_{n,m} \int dv_{\perp} \frac{v_{\perp}}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) \\
 2024 &\cdot \left[\frac{\pi i k_{\parallel}^*}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} \left\{ f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right. \right. \\
 2025 &\quad \left. \left. + f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right\} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

2026

$$\begin{aligned}
 &E^2 = \sum_{n,m} \int dv_{\perp} \frac{v_{\perp}}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) \\
 2027 &\quad \cdot \left[\pi i f_0(v_{\perp}, V) \bar{H}(V) \left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - (m+n)\Omega_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] \right. \right. \\
 2028 &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e][\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + iv_e[n-m]\Omega_e + v_e^2}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} \right\}^{-1} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

2029 Let's pull the summation into the integral and examine the first term:

2030 E^1

$$\begin{aligned}
2031 \quad &= \int dv_{\perp} \frac{\pi i k_{\parallel}^* v_{\perp}}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} \sum_{m,n} \left[\frac{J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right. \\
2032 \quad &\cdot \left. \left\{ 1 + \frac{f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e - iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right)}{f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right)} \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

2033 Now to order of magnitude, the distribution term is unity (f_0 is normalized). Since
2034 H has no poles at $[\omega^* - m\Omega_e \pm iv_e]/k_{\parallel}^*$ by assumption, we can assume the H terms are
2035 of similar magnitude. This means we can treat the ratio in the term in $\{ \}$ as approximately
2036 order unity, allowing us to compare the diagonal vs off diagonal terms. For diagonal
2037 terms, we have the integrand as

$$2038 \quad D(n, n) = \left[\frac{J_n^2(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{[iv_e]} f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right]$$

2039 And for the off-diagonal terms,

$$2040 \quad D(n, m) = \left[\frac{2J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right]$$

2041 The ratio of these two terms is then

$$\begin{aligned}
2042 \quad &\frac{D(n, n)}{D(n, m)} \\
2043 \quad &= \left[\frac{J_n^2(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{[iv_e]} f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right] \\
2044 \quad &\cdot \left[\frac{2J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]} f_0 \left(v_{\perp}, \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) H \left(\frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e + iv_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right) \right]^{-1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$2045 \quad \frac{D(n, n)}{D(n, m)} = \left[\frac{J_n^2(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{[iv_e]} \right] \cdot \frac{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]}{2J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}$$

$$2046 \quad \frac{D(n, n)}{D(n, m)} = \left[\frac{J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)} \right] \cdot \frac{[(m-n)\Omega_e + 2iv_e]}{2iv_e}$$

$$2047 \quad \frac{D(n, n)}{D(n, m)} = \left[\frac{J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)} \right] \cdot \left[(m-n) \frac{\Omega_e}{2iv_e} + 1 \right]$$

2048 So far we have not specified an (n, m) pair and have this general relation. We need
2049 to constrain the ordering of n, m to compare the ratio J_n/J_m . To do this, we make the
2050 assumption of $n < m$, and therefore we compare the magnitude of the $D(n, n)$ term to the
2051 terms $D(n, m > n)$. For example, in looking at the $D(2, 2)$ term, we compare its order of

2052 magnitude to the $D(2,3)$, $D(2,4)$,... terms. The $D(2,1)$ term will be compared to the
 2053 $D(1,1)$ term. With this specification on (n, m) , we have in general

$$2054 \quad J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) > J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)$$

2055 And therefore

$$2056 \quad \frac{D(n, n)}{D(n, m)} = \left[\frac{J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)} \right] \cdot \left[(m - n) \frac{\Omega_e}{2iv_e} + 1 \right] > \left[(m - n) \frac{\Omega_e}{2iv_e} + 1 \right]$$

2057 In the ionosphere, we have $\Omega_e \gg v_e$, and therefore

$$2058 \quad \frac{D(n, n)}{D(n, m)} \gg 1$$

2059 for $m > n$, and we see that for every off-diagonal term, there is a diagonal term
 2060 that is orders of magnitude ($> \Omega_e/v_e$) larger, and we are justified in only taking the
 2061 diagonal terms in the summation.

2062

2063 We now return to the second case, where a different pole is included in the
 2064 integrand. We found

$$2065 \quad E^2 = \sum_{n,m} \int dv_{\perp} \frac{v_{\perp}}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) \\
 2066 \quad \cdot \left[\pi i f_0(v_{\perp}, V) \bar{H}(V) \left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - (m+n)\Omega_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] \right. \right. \\
 2067 \quad \left. \left. + \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e][\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + iv_e[n-m]\Omega_e + v_e^2}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} \right\}^{-1} \right]$$

2068 We can look at the order of magnitude for the integrand again. The diagonal terms
 2069 will be

$$2070 \quad C(n, n) = J_n^2(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) \left[\pi i f_0(v_{\perp}, V) \bar{H}(V) \left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - 2n\Omega_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] \right. \right. \\
 2071 \quad \left. \left. + \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2 + v_e^2}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} \right\}^{-1} \right]$$

2072 And the off-diagonal term is

$$2073 \quad C(n, m) = J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e) \\
 2074 \quad \cdot \left[\pi i f_0(v_{\perp}, V) \bar{H}(V) \left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - (m+n)\Omega_e]}{k_{\parallel}^*} \right] \right. \right. \\
 2075 \quad \left. \left. + \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e][\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + iv_e[n-m]\Omega_e + v_e^2}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}} \right\}^{-1} \right]$$

2076 Taking the ratio again,

$$\begin{aligned}
2077 \quad \frac{C(n, n)}{C(n, m)} &= J_n^2(k_\perp^* \rho_e) \left[\pi i f_0(v_\perp, V) \bar{H}(V) \left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - 2n\Omega_e]}{k_\parallel^*} \right] \right. \right. \\
2078 \quad &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2 + v_e^2}{k_\parallel^{*2}} \right\}^{-1} \right] \\
2079 \quad &\quad \times \left(J_m(k_\perp^* \rho_e) J_n(k_\perp^* \rho_e) \right. \\
2080 \quad &\quad \cdot \left[\pi i f_0(v_\perp, V) \bar{H}(V) \left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - (m+n)\Omega_e]}{k_\parallel^*} \right] \right. \right. \\
2081 \quad &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e][\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + i v_e [n-m]\Omega_e + v_e^2}{k_\parallel^{*2}} \right\}^{-1} \right] \right)^{-1}
\end{aligned}$$

2082 Can simplify this,

$$\begin{aligned}
2083 \quad &\frac{C(n, n)}{C(n, m)} \\
2084 \quad &= \frac{J_n(k_\perp^* \rho_e)}{J_m(k_\perp^* \rho_e)} \\
2085 \quad &\times \frac{\left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - (m+n)\Omega_e]}{k_\parallel^*} \right] + \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e][\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + i v_e [n-m]\Omega_e + v_e^2}{k_\parallel^{*2}} \right\}}{\left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - 2n\Omega_e]}{k_\parallel^*} \right] + \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2 + v_e^2}{k_\parallel^{*2}} \right\}}
\end{aligned}$$

2086 We will again compare the (n, n) term to the (n, m) terms with $m > n$ and
2087 therefore $J_n(k_\perp^* \rho_e) > J_m(k_\perp^* \rho_e)$. We need to look at the fraction, and will write the
2088 numerator in a form that partially cancels the denominator:

$$\begin{aligned}
2089 \quad &\left\{ V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - 2n\Omega_e]}{k_\parallel^*} \right] + \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2 + v_e^2}{k_\parallel^{*2}} - V \left[\frac{[(n-m)\Omega_e]}{k_\parallel^*} \right] \right. \\
2090 \quad &\quad \left. + \frac{([\omega^* - m\Omega_e] - [\omega^* - n\Omega_e])[\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + i v_e [n-m]\Omega_e}{k_\parallel^{*2}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

2091 The fraction is then

$$\begin{aligned}
2092 \quad F &= 1 + \frac{-V \left[\frac{[(n-m)\Omega_e]}{k_\parallel^*} \right] + \frac{([\omega^* - m\Omega_e] - [\omega^* - n\Omega_e])[\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + i v_e [n-m]\Omega_e}{k_\parallel^{*2}}}{V^2 - V \left[\frac{[2\omega^* - 2n\Omega_e]}{k_\parallel^*} \right] + \frac{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2 + v_e^2}{k_\parallel^{*2}}}
\end{aligned}$$

2093 And the ratio of terms becomes

$$2094 \quad \frac{C(n, n)}{C(n, m)} = \frac{J_n(k_\perp^* \rho_e)}{J_m(k_\perp^* \rho_e)} \times F > F$$

2095 Where we've used the constraint of J_n/J_m . Now the phase velocity V of this 3rd
 2096 pole is completely unspecified. If the pole V is large compared to the velocities $\omega^*/k_{\parallel}^*$,
 2097 $\Omega_e/k_{\parallel}^*$, and $v_e/k_{\parallel}^*$, then we have to leading order $F \approx 1 + \frac{V}{v_e^2} \approx 1$ and therefore
 2098 $C(n, n) > C(n, m)$ for $m > n$. For $k_{\perp}^* \rho_e < 1$, the ratio $J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)/J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)$ is typically a
 2099 factor of 2 or larger, so we can roughly say $C(n, n) \gg C(n, m)$ and drop the off-diagonal
 2100 terms as desired when V is large.

2101 Now if V is small, we have to leading order

$$2102 \quad F = 1 + \frac{([\omega^* - m\Omega_e] - [\omega^* - n\Omega_e])[\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + iv_e[n - m]\Omega_e}{k_{\parallel}^{*2}([\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2 + v_e^2)}$$

$$2103 \quad F = 1 + \frac{([\omega^* - m\Omega_e] - [\omega^* - n\Omega_e])[\omega^* - n\Omega_e] + iv_e[n - m]\Omega_e}{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2 + v_e^2}$$

2104 If we happen to be at a resonance and $\omega^* \approx n\Omega_e$, then

$$2105 \quad F_{res,n} = 1 + \frac{iv_e[n - m]\Omega_e}{v_e^2} = 1 + \frac{i[n - m]\Omega_e}{v_e} \gg 1$$

2106 Based on $\Omega_e \gg v_e$, and therefore $C(n, n) \gg C(n, m)$ as desired. If we happen to
 2107 be at a resonance where $\omega^* \approx m\Omega_e$, then $[\omega^* - n\Omega_e] \gg v_e$ (either ω^* is large, or $\Omega_e >$
 2108 ω^*):

$$2109 \quad F_{res,m} = 1 + \frac{-[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2 + iv_e[n - m]\Omega_e}{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2 + v_e^2} = 1 + \frac{-[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2 + iv_e[n - m]\Omega_e}{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2}$$

$$2110 \quad F_{res,m} = 1 - 1 + \frac{iv_e[n - m]\Omega_e}{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2} = \frac{iv_e[n - m]\Omega_e}{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2} \gg 0$$

2111 And we have $C(n, n) \gg C(n, m)$ as desired. If we are not at any resonance, then
 2112 $[\omega^* - n\Omega_e] \gg v_e$ and similarly $[\omega^* - m\Omega_e] \gg v_e$, so to leading order,

$$2113 \quad F = 1 + \frac{([\omega^* - m\Omega_e] - [\omega^* - n\Omega_e])[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]}{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2} = 1 + \frac{([\omega^* - m\Omega_e] - [\omega^* - n\Omega_e])}{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]}$$

$$2114 \quad F = 1 + \frac{([\omega^* - m\Omega_e] - [\omega^* - n\Omega_e])[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]}{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]^2} = 1 - 1 + \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e]}{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]}$$

$$2115 \quad = \frac{[\omega^* - m\Omega_e]}{[\omega^* - n\Omega_e]}$$

2116 If the ω^* factor is larger than either Ω_e factor, then $F \approx 1$ and $\frac{C(n,n)}{C(n,m)} \approx \frac{J_n}{J_m} \gg 1$ as
 2117 determined before. If the Ω_e terms are dominant, then we have been comparing the terms
 2118 with $m > n$, and therefore $F \approx \frac{m\Omega_e}{n\Omega_e} > 1$.

2119 Effectively, for any extra pole in the integral, the diagonal terms of the
 2120 residue end up being dominant. This does rely on $k_{\perp}^* \rho_e \leq 1$, which should hold in the
 2121 ionosphere. For $k_{\perp}^* \rho_e \ll 1$, the diagonal terms become even more dominant.

2122 The order of magnitude of the residues allows us to make the approximation that

$$2123 \quad E = \int dv_{\parallel} dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} f_0(\vec{v}) \sum_{n,m} \frac{J_m(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{\omega^* - k_{\parallel}^* v_{\parallel} - m\Omega_e - iv_e} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{\omega^* - k_{\parallel}^* v_{\parallel} - n\Omega_e + iv_e} H(v_{\parallel})$$

2124 Can be simplified to only the diagonal terms in the summation:

$$2125 \quad E = \int dv_{\parallel} dv_{\perp} v_{\perp} f_0(\vec{v}) \sum_n \frac{J_n^2(k_{\perp}^* \rho_e)}{\omega^* - k_{\parallel}^* v_{\parallel} - n\Omega_e - iv_e} \frac{1}{\omega^* - k_{\parallel}^* v_{\parallel} - n\Omega_e + iv_e} H(v_{\parallel})$$

2126 Note: In working out the full result, the $\langle T \rangle_a$ terms ended up with several mis-matched
2127 poles of the form

$$2128 \quad \sum_n \int dv_{\parallel} \frac{J_n(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\left\{ v_{\parallel} - \frac{\omega - n\Omega_{ce} - iv_e}{k_{\parallel}} \right\}} \frac{J_{n-1}(k_{\perp} \rho_e)}{\left\{ v_{\parallel} - \frac{\omega - (n-1)\Omega_{ce} - iv_e}{k_{\parallel}} \right\}}$$

2129 In each calculation, these terms with mis-matched poles evaluated to much smaller values
2130 than similar terms where the poles were matched, meaning $v_{\parallel} - (\omega - n\Omega_{ce} \pm iv_e)/k_{\parallel}$.
2131 This further justifies diagonalizing the double summations to only end up with matching
2132 sets of poles.

2133

2134

2135 **Appendix E: Photoelectron Distribution**

2136 The solutions utilize a photoelectron distribution of the form $f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$. The numeric
2137 integration means the photoelectron distribution can be numerically defined, as long as
2138 care is taken with its derivatives. In previous work we were able to evaluate the Plemelj
2139 formula for $v_{\parallel}$ easily, and convert the distribution into energy units, $f_{0h}(E)$. We will not
2140 make this step in this paper for two reasons: 1) The extra work involved in converting the
2141 distribution to energy units, and more importantly 2) The ability to use an anisotropic
2142 photoelectron distribution.

2143 We keep the equations in the form $f_{0h}(v_{\perp}, v_{\parallel})$, however we still need a model
2144 photoelectron distribution to work with. As before, we take an oversimplified
2145 distribution: isotropic Gaussian peaks at discrete energies, with a power law tail. This
2146 takes the form of

$$2147 \quad f_{0h}(\vec{v}) = c_1 v^{-p} + \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \exp\left(-\frac{(v - V_i)^2}{\delta_i^2}\right)$$

2148 Where A_i is the relative power of a photoelectron peak at speed V_i , with Gaussian
2149 width δ_i . We want to normalize this such that

$$2150 \quad \int d\vec{v}^3 f_{0h}(\vec{v}) = 1$$

2151 Noting that we have defined the distribution as isotropic, that is only dependent
2152 on v , we have

2153
$$\int d\vec{v}^3 f_{0h}(\vec{v}) = 4\pi \int_0^\infty dv v^2 f_{0h}(v)$$

2154 Then

2155
$$4\pi \int_0^\infty dv v^2 f_{0h}(v) = 4\pi \int_0^\infty dv v^2 \left[c_1 v^{-p} + \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \exp\left(-\frac{(v - V_i)^2}{\delta_i^2}\right) \right]$$

2156 First look at the power law tail,

2157
$$I_{tail} = 4\pi c_1 \int_0^\infty dv v^2 v^{-p} = 4\pi c_1 \int_0^\infty dv v^{2-p}$$

2158

2159 This does not converge at $v = 0$, and only converges if $p > 3$. We deal with the
 2160 nonconvergence at 0 noting that we have the thermal population at low velocities, so we
 2161 change the lower bounds,

2162
$$I_{tail} = \int_{v_{min}}^\infty dv v^{2-p}$$

2163
$$I_{tail} = 4\pi c_1 \left[\frac{v^{3-p}}{3-p} \right]_{v_{min}}^\infty$$

2164
$$I_{tail} = 4\pi c_1 \left[\frac{\infty^{3-p}}{3-p} - \frac{v_{min}^{3-p}}{3-p} \right]$$

2165 We required $p > 3$, so $3 - p < 0$ and we see the first term goes to 0, and we have

2166
$$I_{tail} = 4\pi c_1 \frac{v_{min}^{-(p-3)}}{p-3}$$

2167 We want the integrated values of the peaks to each be normalized to A_i ,
 2168 and the power law tail normalized to c_1 , so that the entire integral is $\int d\vec{v}^3 f_{0h} = c_1 +$
 2169 $\sum_i A_i$. This means we need the power law tail to be

2170
$$f_{tail} = c_1 \frac{v_{min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} v^{-p} = c_1 \frac{v_{min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} v^{-p}$$

2171 We now move on to the Gaussian bumps. We have

2172
$$I_G = 4\pi \int_0^\infty dv v^2 \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \exp\left(-\frac{(v - V_i)^2}{\delta_i^2}\right)$$

2173
$$I_G = 4\pi \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\delta_i^3} \int_0^\infty dv v^2 \exp\left(-\frac{(v - V_i)^2}{\delta_i^2}\right)$$

2174 We should recognize here that we could actually do these integrals as

2175
$$I_G = \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 \exp\left(-\frac{(v - V_i)^2}{\delta_i^2}\right)$$

2176 Where we cover all of $\mathbb{R}^3$ with the velocity. Therefore we can do a change of
 2177 coordinates for each integral, $\vec{v} \rightarrow \vec{v} - \vec{V}_i$ and obtain

2178
$$I_G = \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \int_{\vec{v}} d\vec{v}^3 \exp\left(-\frac{v^2}{\delta_i^2}\right)$$

2179 In other words, we integrate over the Gaussian without care that it is shifted off
 2180 the origin. Then

2181
$$I_G = 4\pi \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \int_0^\infty dv v^2 \exp\left(-\frac{v^2}{\delta_i^2}\right)$$

2182
$$I_G = 4\pi \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \delta_i^3}{4}$$

2183
$$I_G = \sum_i A_i$$

2184 Which is by design in how we normalized each peak to have strength A_i .
 2185 Therefore, the total area under f_{0h} is

2186
$$\int d\vec{v}^3 f_{0h}(\vec{v}) = c_1 + \sum_i A_i$$

2187 The normalized photoelectron distribution with several Gaussian peaks,
 2188 and a power law tail starting at v_{min} is then

2189
$$f_{0h}(\vec{v}) = \frac{c_1 \frac{v_{min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} v^{-p} + \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \exp\left(-\frac{(v - V_i)^2}{\delta_i^2}\right)}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i}$$

2190 In practice, this normalization is slightly off, so we integrate this again and divide by the
 2191 result.

2192 We want to evaluate this in terms of $v_\perp, v_\parallel$ components, so we use $v =$

2193
$$\sqrt{v_\perp^2 + v_\parallel^2}:$$

2194
$$f_{0h}(\vec{v}) = \frac{c_1 \frac{v_{min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} (v_\perp^2 + v_\parallel^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}} + \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \exp\left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_\perp^2 + v_\parallel^2} - V_i\right)^2}{\delta_i^2}\right)}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i}$$

2195 We will want derivatives of this distribution with respect to $v_\perp$ and $v_\parallel$. These have the
 2196 same form:

$$\begin{aligned}
2197 \quad \frac{\partial f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel}} &= \frac{1}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i} \left\{ -pc_1 \frac{v_{min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} v_{\parallel} (v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-1} \right. \\
2198 \quad &\quad \left. - \sum_i \frac{2A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \frac{v_{\parallel} \left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2199 \quad \frac{\partial f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\perp}} &= \frac{1}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i} \left\{ -pc_1 \frac{v_{min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} v_{\perp} (v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-1} \right. \\
2200 \quad &\quad \left. - \sum_i \frac{2A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \frac{v_{\perp} \left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

2201

2202

2203

We also want the 3 second order derivatives:

$$\begin{aligned}
2204 \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel}^2} &= \frac{1}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i} \left\{ -pc_1 \frac{v_{min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} v_{\parallel} (v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-1} \right. \\
2205 \quad &\quad \left. - \sum_i \frac{2A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \frac{v_{\parallel} \left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$2206 \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel}^2} = \frac{1}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i} \left\{ -pc_1 \frac{v_{min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} \left[(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-1} + v_{\parallel} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} (v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-1} \right] \right.$$

$$2207 \quad - \sum_i \frac{2A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \left[\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \right.$$

$$2208 \quad + v_{\parallel} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \left.$$

$$2209 \quad + \frac{v_{\parallel} \left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\parallel}} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \right] \left. \right\}$$

$$2210 \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel}^2} = \frac{1}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i} \left\{ -pc_1 \frac{v_{min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} \left[(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-1} - (p+2)v_{\parallel}^2 (v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-2} \right] \right.$$

$$2211 \quad - \sum_i \frac{2A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \left[\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \right.$$

$$2212 \quad + \frac{v_{\parallel}}{\delta_i^2} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \frac{V_i v_{\parallel}}{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} \right)^3}$$

$$2213 \quad - 2 \frac{v_{\parallel}^2 \left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^4 (v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \left. \right] \left. \right\}$$

$$2214 \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel}^2} = \frac{1}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i} \left\{ -pc_1 \frac{v_{\min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} \left[(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-1} - (p+2)v_{\parallel}^2(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-2} \right] \right.$$

$$2215 \quad - \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2}\delta_i^3} \frac{2}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \left[\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} \right. \right.$$

$$2216 \quad \left. - V_i \right) + \frac{V_i v_{\parallel}^2}{(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)} - 2 \frac{v_{\parallel}^2 \left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \left. \right\}$$

2217

2218 Easy to pick off the $v_{\parallel}$ factors and replace with $v_{\perp}$ to obtain

$$2219 \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\perp}^2} = \frac{1}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i} \left\{ -pc_1 \frac{v_{\min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} \left[(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-1} - (p+2)v_{\perp}^2(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-2} \right] \right.$$

$$2220 \quad - \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2}\delta_i^3} \frac{2}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \left[\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} \right. \right.$$

$$2221 \quad \left. - V_i \right) + \frac{V_i v_{\perp}^2}{(v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)} - 2 \frac{v_{\perp}^2 \left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \left. \right\}$$

2222 The mixed derivative is then

$$2223 \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel} \partial v_{\perp}} = \frac{1}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i} \left\{ -pc_1 \frac{v_{\min}^{(p-3)}(p-3)}{4\pi} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} v_{\parallel} (v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-1} \right.$$

$$2224 \quad \left. - \sum_i \frac{2A_i}{\pi^{3/2}\delta_i^3} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \frac{v_{\parallel} \left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i \right)^2}{\delta_i^2} \right) \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2225 \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel} v_{\perp}} &= \frac{1}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i} \left\{ c_1 \frac{v_{\min}^{(p-3)} (p-3)}{4\pi} p(p+2) v_{\perp} v_{\parallel} (v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-2} \right. \\
2226 \quad &\quad \left. - \sum_i \frac{2A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \left[\exp\left(-\frac{(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i)^2}{\delta_i^2}\right) \frac{v_{\parallel}}{\delta_i^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \frac{(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i)}{\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \right. \right. \\
2227 \quad &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{v_{\parallel} (\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i)}{\delta_i^2 \sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\perp}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i)^2}{\delta_i^2}\right) \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2228 \quad \frac{\partial^2 f_{0h}}{\partial v_{\parallel} v_{\perp}} &= \frac{1}{c_1 + \sum_i A_i} \left\{ c_1 \frac{v_{\min}^{(p-3)} (p-3)}{4\pi} p(p+2) v_{\perp} v_{\parallel} (v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)^{-\frac{p}{2}-2} \right. \\
2229 \quad &\quad \left. - \sum_i \frac{A_i}{\pi^{3/2} \delta_i^3} \frac{2v_{\perp} v_{\parallel}}{\delta_i^2 (v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2)} \exp\left(-\frac{(\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i)^2}{\delta_i^2}\right) \left[\frac{V_i}{\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2}} \right. \right. \\
2230 \quad &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{2}{\delta_i^2} (\sqrt{v_{\perp}^2 + v_{\parallel}^2} - V_i)^2 \right] \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

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